

Extreme Food Risk Analytics

D7.1.3: Project Management Handbook

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EFRA Consortium			
#	Participant Organisation Number	Short name	Country
1	AGROKNOW IKE	AGROKNOW	EL
2	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	CSR	IT
3	STOCKHOLMS UNIVERSITET	SU	SE
4	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	WR	NL
5	JAKALA S.p.A. S.B.	JAKALA	IT
6	AGRIVI DOO ZA PROIZVODNJU TRGOVINUI USLUGE	AGRIVI DOO	HR
7	RAINNO IDIOTIKI KEFALAIOUCHIKI ETAIREIA	RAINNO	EL
8	SGS ROMANIA SA	SGS ROMANIA	RO
9	MOY PARK LTD	MOY PARK	UK

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviations / Acronyms	Meaning
CM	Communication Manager
DEM	Deliverable Type: Demonstrator
DPCO	Deputy Project Coordinator
DPCO	Deputy Project Coordinator
EB	Executive Board
GGroups	Google Groups
FDA	United States Food and Drug Administration
FM	Financial Manager
GMeet	Google Meet
ISC	International Steering Committee
PB	Project Board
PC	Project Consortium
PCO	Project Coordinator
PMH	Project Management Handbook
R	Deliverable Type: Report
QA	Quality Assurance
QC	Quality Control
QI	Quality Improvement
TL	Task Leader
TM	Technical Manager
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

1. Executive Summary

This deliverable constitutes the 3rd version of the EFRA Project Management Handbook (PMH). It consolidates and updates all management, quality assurance and risk-related procedures applied during the project, reflecting the experience gained and the mechanisms implemented throughout the project's lifecycle. As the core operational reference for the Project Consortium (PC), this document ensures that all partners follow consistent, transparent and compliant practices aligned with the Grant Agreement and the Description of the Action.

The deliverable covers three main areas:

- Project management and reporting, including the organisational structure, decision-making mechanisms, communication processes, reporting obligations, financial management and the procedures for producing and submitting milestones and deliverables.
- Quality assurance and monitoring, describing the quality plan defined in earlier versions (D7.1.1 and D7.1.2) and how it was applied in practice. This includes the QA–QC–QI cycle, quality criteria, review processes for report-oriented and software-oriented deliverables, and the tools and templates used to ensure consistency, traceability and compliance.
- Risk assessment and contingency actions, outlining the continuous process used to identify, analyse, classify and monitor both foreseen and unforeseen risks. It also details the mitigation and contingency measures applied, the risk matrix methodology and the mechanisms used to ensure timely detection and response.

Across these areas, the handbook provides clear procedures for:

- Coordinating the Project Consortium (PC) and ensuring timely delivery of project outputs
- Managing communication within the Project Consortium (PC) and with external stakeholders, including the European Commission
- Ensuring quality, consistency and compliance across all deliverables and software releases
- Monitoring financial and contractual obligations
- Identifying, assessing and mitigating risks throughout the project

The primary goal of this deliverable is to support all EFRA partners in carrying out their responsibilities efficiently and coherently. By defining common processes, templates, roles and decision-making pathways, it ensures smooth collaboration between the management team, Work Package leaders and all consortium members. This third version of the handbook therefore serves as the definitive reference for organising, executing and monitoring day-to-day project work until project completion.

2. Introduction

The EFRA Project Management Handbook provides the operational framework for the effective day-to-day management of the project. It brings together all procedures related to project coordination, reporting, quality assurance, monitoring and risk management. This deliverable serves as a practical reference for all partners, ensuring that activities are carried out consistently, transparently and in full alignment with the Grant Agreement and the Description of the Action.

2.1. Scope

This deliverable outlines the management structure, processes and tools that support the implementation of EFRA. It describes in detail:

- the project management and reporting procedures
- the quality assurance and monitoring mechanisms
- the risk assessment, mitigation and contingency planning processes

As such, it functions as the EFRA Project Handbook, defining how Quality Assurance (QA) is embedded into the project's structure and daily operations. The handbook covers:

- responsibilities of all partners involved in project activities
- internal and external monitoring and reporting procedures
- milestone and deliverable appraisal and submission processes
- the external project review procedure

2.2. Audience

This deliverable is primarily intended for EFRA project partners, providing them with the procedures, responsibilities and quality requirements necessary for their work. It also serves as a reference for the European Commission, demonstrating the management, quality assurance and risk mitigation mechanisms applied throughout the project.

2.3. Structure

The Project Management Handbook is organised into the following main sections, providing guidance and practical instructions to support efficient collaboration across the Project Consortium (PC).

- Section 2 presents the Scope, Audience and Structure of the document.
- Section 3 describes the project management and reporting framework, including the organisational structure, decision-making mechanisms, communication processes, reporting obligations, milestones, deliverable procedures and financial management rules.
- Section 4 outlines the quality assurance and monitoring processes, including quality criteria, review procedures and the templates used for deliverables and internal documents.
- Section 5 details the risk management framework, covering risk identification, analysis, mitigation and contingency planning.
- Section 6 provides the conclusions of the deliverable.
- Annex I: EFRA templates for deliverables, presentations, meeting agendas and related documents.
- Annex II: Templates for internal progress and financial reporting.

3. Project Management and Reporting

3.1. Management Structure, Milestones and Procedures

3.1.1. Overview

The EFRA Project Consortium (PC) brings together 9 partners from 7 European countries, forming a multidisciplinary collaboration that combines scientific, technical, industrial, and data-driven expertise. This diverse partnership enables EFRA to address complex challenges across the agri-food value chain while ensuring strong alignment with European priorities on data, interoperability, and sustainability. The PC's work is grounded in close coordination, transparent communication, and shared responsibility for achieving the project's objectives. The names and acronyms used throughout project communications are listed in **Table 1**.

Table 1: List of EFRA Beneficiaries

#	Partner name	Partner short name	Country	Project Entry Date	Project Exit Date
1	AGROKNOW IKE	AGROKNOW	Greece	M1	M36
2	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	CNR	Italy	M1	M36
3	STOCKHOLMS UNIVERSITET	SU	Sweden	M1	M36
4	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	WR	Netherlands	M1	M36
5	JAKALA S.p.A. S.B.	JAKALA	Italy	M1	M36
6	AGRIVI DOO ZA PROIZVODNJU TRGOVINUI USLUGE	AGRIVI DOO	Croatia	M1	M36
7	RAINNO IDIOTIKI KEFALAIOUCHIKI ETAIREIA	RAINNO	Greece	M1	M36
8	SGS ROMANIA SA	SGS ROMANIA	Romania	M1	M36
9	MOY PARK LTD	MOY PARK	United Kingdom	M1	M36

The collaboration within the Project Consortium and with the European Commission is governed by the Grant Agreement (GA), originally signed on December 1st, 2022, and subsequently updated through an amendment approved on November 20th, 2023. The GA, together with the Description of Action (Part A and Part B) and Annex 2 (Estimated Budget), provides the formal framework for the project's implementation. Complementing the GA, the Consortium Agreement (CA), prepared by the Project Coordinator and signed by all partners at project start, defines the internal operational rules, including decision-making procedures, communication protocols, and conflict-resolution mechanisms. Both the GA and CA are accessible through the project's shared collaboration space (Google shared folder).

During the project lifetime, the Project Consortium composition evolved due to corporate changes among beneficiaries. The partner MAIZE underwent a universal takeover (UTRO) and was fully integrated into JAKALA, with the takeover officially completed on July 1st, 2025. In accordance with Horizon Europe procedures, Jakala automatically assumed all rights and obligations under the GA. This type of change does not require a formal amendment. Instead, the LEAR updated the Participant Register and submitted the necessary legal documentation for validation. Although the formal update in the EC Participant Portal was

completed towards the end of the project, JAKALA had already been incorporated into EFRA's dissemination and communication materials from September 1st, 2026, ensuring continuity in project representation. Similarly, Moy Park, an associated partner, became part of the Pilgrim's Europe Group during the project. Despite this corporate integration, Moy Park retained its legal entity status (including VAT number), which is why project documentation may refer to the organisation either as Moy Park or Moy Park (Pilgrim's Europe) depending on context.

The governance structure defined in the GA and detailed in Section 6 of the CA establishes the roles, responsibilities, and procedures that guide EFRA's management. It specifies practical elements such as meeting schedules, agenda requirements, voting rules, and veto rights. EFRA's management relies on three main bodies, the Project Board (PB), the Executive Board (EB), and the Project Coordinator (PCO), which jointly support, guide, and oversee the implementation of the project and the achievement of its objectives. Their roles and responsibilities are presented in the following sections.

3.1.2. Organisational Structure and Decision-making Mechanisms

The organisational structure of EFRA is designed to provide strong, transparent, and flexible management capable of supporting the evolving needs of a multi-partner, multi-country Horizon Europe project. Given the diversity of the PC and the technical complexity of the work, the management framework ensures that all project components are coherently linked, that communication flows smoothly across partners, and that interactions with the European Commission and external stakeholders are consistent and well-coordinated.

The management framework covers all levels of the project, from individual technical tasks to cross-WP coordination and strategic oversight. The decision-making structure reflects the project's complexity and ensures that decisions can be taken efficiently, with clear escalation paths and well-defined responsibilities. The structure combines traditional project management roles with flexible communication channels and workflows, enabling the PC to adapt to emerging needs, risks, and opportunities.

The management approach has been developed to:

- Ensure effective, transparent, and accountable management of EFRA.
- Establish clear procedures for decision-making and conflict resolution.
- Implement robust quality control processes for all outputs and deliverables.
- Ensure that the project progresses within the approved budget and complies with administrative, financial, and legal requirements at EU and national levels.
- Ensure that all partners fulfil their obligations under the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.
- Manage background and foreground intellectual property in accordance with the GA and CA.
- Address ethical, data protection, and gender-related considerations appropriately and consistently.

3.1.3. Management Clusters and Responsibilities

This section presents the project's management bodies, their appointed members, and their responsibilities. The EFRA management structure is composed of the Project Coordinator (PCO), the Financial Manager (FM), the Technical Manager (TM), the Project Board (PB), and the Executive Board (EB). Together, these bodies ensure coherent strategic direction, operational coordination, and quality assurance across the project.

3.1.3.1. Project Coordinator (PCO), Financial Manager (FM) and Technical Manager™

The Project Coordinator (PCO) is the partner ultimately responsible for the execution and strategic management of EFRA. The PCO ensures that the project follows the agreed strategy, oversees the selection and implementation of methodologies, supervises monitoring activities, and coordinates the quality assurance function. In day-to-day operations, the PCO manages operational coordination, internal

communication, and administrative follow-up, ensuring that decisions taken by the Project Board (PB) and the Executive Board (EB) are implemented effectively.

EFRA is coordinated by Agroknow IKE (Greece).

Project Coordination Team:

- Dr. Charalampos (Babis) Thanopoulos (Agroknow) - Project Coordinator (PCO). Responsible for overall project leadership, internal quality assurance, legal and administrative oversight, and strategic coordination.
- Dr. Giannis Stoitsis (Agroknow) - Deputy Project Coordinator (DPCO), acting on behalf of the PCO when required.
- Mrs. Francesca Tsaropoulou (Agroknow) - Administrative and Financial Manager (FM). Responsible for financial monitoring, partner cost follow-up, and coordination of payments across the Project Consortium (PC).

Technical Management:

The Technical Manager (TM) oversees all technical activities, ensuring coherence across WPs, monitoring technical progress, and guiding the integration of all EFRA services and components.

- Mr. Alessio Bosca (JAKALA) - Technical Manager (TM).

PCO's Responsibilities:

- Overall scientific, administrative, and financial management of EFRA.
- Chairing the Project Board (PB) and Executive Board (EB).
- Preparing agendas, documentation, and decisions for PB and EB meetings.
- Collecting, validating, and preparing financial information (cost statements, supporting documents, audit certificates) for submission to the European Commission.
- Ensuring the timely delivery of all documents, software, datasets, and deliverables described in the Grant Agreement or requested by the Commission during reviews and audits.
- Acting as the single intermediary for all communication between the Project Consortium (PC) and the European Commission, including correspondence with the Project Officer (PO) and dissemination of PO decisions to partners.

PCO's Authorisations

In addition to the responsibilities described above, the PCO is formally authorised to:

- Request a letter of comfort from any partner for which there are serious concerns regarding financial soundness, to ensure that the partner can fulfil its obligations under the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. Until such proof is provided, the PCO may withhold the disbursement of EC funds to that partner.
- Withhold payments (in consultation with the EC Project Officer) if a partner is late in submitting, or refuses to provide, deliverables or reports as defined in the GA or CA.

It is important to note that none of these escalation or enforcement mechanisms were activated during the EFRA project. Collaboration among partners remained consistently smooth, constructive, and transparent throughout the project lifetime. No financial concerns, or conflicts requiring formal intervention occurred, and all partners fulfilled their obligations in a timely and cooperative manner.

3.1.3.2. Project Board (PB)

The Project Board (PB) is the formal decision-making body and the highest level of management within EFRA. It provides strategic oversight, ensures alignment with the Grant Agreement, and validates major decisions affecting the project's direction, resources, and governance. The PB is composed of one senior Management Representative from each consortium partner (or a formally delegated representative), together with the PCO.

Composition

Each partner appoints one voting representative to the PB. These representatives must hold sufficient authority within their organisations to commit to PB decisions. They are responsible for the internal coordination of EFRA activities within their institution and for ensuring that decisions taken at PB level are implemented locally. The PB is formally empowered by the Consortium Agreement to take high-level decisions that affect the project.

Tasks and Responsibilities

The PB is the highest collective decision-making body of EFRA. It is responsible for decisions related to:

- The overall management, planning, and control of the project, based on progress reports from the Executive Board (EB).
- The identification of strategic goals and approval of implementation plans for each Work Package.
- All budget-related matters, including approval of periodic financial reports and forecasts for upcoming periods.
- The structure and restructuring of Work Packages, if required.
- The definition and approval of project-wide standards, including quality assurance procedures, the EFRA assessment protocol, technical architecture standards, scientific guidelines, and the valorisation approach.
- The appointment of members of the Executive Board.
- The acceptance of new partners and the exclusion of existing partners, when necessary.
- Amendments to the Consortium Agreement.
- The resolution of disputes or difficulties escalated from the EB or individual partners.
- Decisions regarding premature termination or completion of the project.
- While the PB does not engage in day-to-day management, its decisions have a direct impact on operational execution.

Meetings

Ordinary PB meetings are held at least twice per year, either in person or online, with participation from all partners. Additional meetings may be called at any time by: (i) the Chairperson, (ii) 2 BP members, or (iii) at least one quarter ($\frac{1}{4}$) of PB members. A quorum is reached when more than half of the partners are present or represented by proxy. The European Commission may participate as an observer.

The PCO convenes PB meetings and circulates the agenda at least fifteen (15) days in advance, including all relevant background information for decision-making. No decision may be taken on items not listed on the agenda unless unanimously agreed by all present or represented partners.

In exceptional cases, PB decisions may be taken remotely (e.g., via email or teleconference) through consultation by the Chairperson. Such decisions must be ratified at the next ordinary PB meeting.

Minutes are circulated to all partners without delay and are considered approved if no objections are raised within 30 calendar days.

Voting

PB decisions are taken by simple majority. In case of a tie, the PCO, acting as Chairperson, casts the deciding vote. A partner may issue a veto only in the following cases:

- When accepting a new partner poses a substantial threat to its commercial or strategic interests that cannot be resolved by other means.
- When a decision significantly affects its allocated budget or workload as defined in the Description of Action.

Vetoes may be overruled under specific conditions:

- For case (a): by unanimous vote of all non-objecting partners, representing more than two-thirds ($\frac{2}{3}$) of all partners.
- For case (b): by a three-quarters ($\frac{3}{4}$) majority of partners present or represented.

Project Board Structure

The PB structure, including the representatives of all partners and their deputies, is presented in **Table 2**.

Table 2: EFRA Project Board (PB) structure

#	Organisation	Partner Representative	Deputy
1	AGROKNOW	Babis Thanopoulos	Giannis Stoitsis
2	CNR	Raffaele Perego	Franco Maria Nardini
3	SU	Aron Henriksson	Tony Lindgren
4	WR	Bas van der Velden	Ali Hurriyetoglu
5	JAKALA	Alessio Bosca	Marco Trevisan
6	AGRIVI DOO	Morgane Rumeau	Tanja Matosevic
7	RAINNO	Grigoris Matenoglou	Stavros Tsitouras
8	SGS ROMANIA	Anna Romanova	Martina Hladká
9	MOY PARK	Anne Richmond	Hollie Bradford

3.1.3.3. Executive Board (EB)

The Executive Board (EB) is responsible for the day-to-day operational management of EFRA and reports directly to the Project Board (PB). It ensures the coherent implementation of all project activities, facilitates coordination among partners, and oversees the administrative, technical, and procedural execution of the project in line with the Grant Agreement (GA) and the Consortium Agreement (CA). The EB also acts as the primary liaison mechanism between partners for the analysis, validation, and approval of results generated within the Work Packages (WPs).

The EB is responsible for the day-to-day management of the project and shall report and be accountable to the PB. This involves assuming overall responsibility for liaison between the Parties in relation to the Project, for analysing and approving the results, for proper administration of the project and for implementation of the provisions contained in the Grant and Consortium Agreements.

Composition

The EB is composed of all Work Package Leaders (WPLs), each responsible for managing the operational activities within their respective WPs. Members of the EB are nominated by their organisations and formally approved by the PB. This structure ensures that all technical, scientific, and operational dimensions of the project are represented in the decision-making process.

Tasks and Responsibilities

Under the strategic direction of the PB, the EB coordinates the implementation of the EFRA project and ensures that all activities progress according to plan. Its responsibilities include:

- Taking necessary decisions between PB meetings to ensure continuity of project operations.
- Supporting the PCO in fulfilling obligations towards the European Commission.
- Ensuring that all work meets the functional, technical, and scientific requirements defined in the Description of Action.
- Providing administrative, financial, legal, and logistical support (through the coordinator) for activities that extend beyond individual WPs.
- Supporting WP Leaders in monitoring progress, including the administration of milestones, deliverables, and deadlines.
- Compiling internal progress reports based on inputs from WP Leaders and Partner Contact Points and submitting them to the PB.
- Supporting the PB in preparing periodic technical and financial reports for submission to the Commission.
- Reviewing and proposing budget transfers in accordance with the GA and annual implementation plans.
- Proposing changes in work allocation, budget distribution, or partner participation to the PB when necessary.
- Making proposals to the Project Consortium (excluding any Defaulting Party) regarding the reassignment of tasks from a Defaulting Party, if such a situation arises.
- WPLs are responsible for collecting status and progress information from all partners active within their WP for each reporting period.

Meetings

The EB may meet physically or virtually. Ordinary EB meetings are held at least quarterly and for the case of RP2 every month virtually, convened by the Chairperson. Additional meetings may be called at any time by:

- the Chairperson,
- two EB members, or
- at least one quarter ($\frac{1}{4}$) of EB members.

The European Commission may participate as an observer.

In addition to the quarterly meetings, the EB and the PCO met monthly via videoconference. During these meetings, each WPL provided an update on the status of their WP, enabling continuous monitoring and early identification of risks or delays. Monthly calls were scheduled in advance on a fixed day (every 2nd Thursday of each month), while shorter follow-up meetings (30 minutes) were held on the 4th Thursday of each month to track actions and progress.

Meetings are convened by the Chairperson with at least 15 calendar days' notice, including an agenda and relevant background information. A quorum is reached when at least three voting members are present or represented by proxy.

Decisions requiring a vote must be identified on the pre-meeting agenda unless unanimously agreed otherwise by all present or represented members, provided that at least three-quarters ($\frac{3}{4}$) of EB members are present or represented.

Minutes summarising the decisions taken and the actions agreed among all WP Leaders were included within the meeting agenda, circulated without delay, and considered approved if no objections were raised within 15 calendar days. Once approved, minutes were shared with all consortium partners. All meeting agendas and supporting documents are available in the project's Shared Folder, ensuring that every partner can consult them at any time.

Voting

Each member of the Executive Board has one vote: the Chairperson (PCO, or their substitute when necessary) and the 7 Work Package Leaders. Decisions are taken in accordance with the voting rules defined in the Consortium Agreement and the procedures described above.

Executive Board Synthesis

The composition of the Executive Board, including all Work Package Leaders and their deputies, is presented in Table 3. This table reflects the operational leadership of each Work Package and ensures that all technical and scientific domains of EFRA are represented in the project's day-to-day decision-making.

Table 3: EFRA Executive Board (EB) structure

WP	Lead partner	Partner Representative	Deputy
WP1	WR	Bas van der Velden	Ali Hurriyetoglu
WP2	SU	Aron Henriksson	Korbinian Randl
WP3	CNR	Franco Maria Nardini	Salvatore Trani
WP4	JAKALA	Alessio Bosca	Marco Trevisan
WP5	AGROKNOW	Iraklis Posnakidis	Babis Thanopoulos
WP6	RAINNO	Grigoris Matenoglou	Stavros Tsitouras
WP7	AGROKNOW	Babis Thanopoulos	Francesca Tsaropoulou

3.1.3.4. Task Leaders (TL)

Apart from the Executive Board (EB) that is composed by the WP leaders and deputies, EFRA has also assigned specific Task Leaders for every task within each WP, to ensure a smooth project implementation and ownership of all project tasks and deliverables. The following **Table 4** lists the task leaders and deputy task leaders for all tasks in the EFRA.

In addition to the Executive Board (EB), which is composed of the Work Package Leaders and their deputies, EFRA has appointed Task Leaders for every task within each Work Package. This structure ensures smooth project implementation, clear ownership of activities, and accountability for all technical and operational outcomes. Task Leaders are responsible for coordinating the work within their task, monitoring progress, ensuring timely delivery of outputs, and liaising with their respective WP Leaders.

Table 4: Task Leaders and deputies

WP	Task	Lead partner	Task lead	Deputy
WP1	T1.1 Scientific requirements on short- and long-term food risk prediction	WR	Ali Hurriyetoglu	Bas van der Velden
	T1.2 Heterogeneous data mining requirements (sources & types)	JAKALA	Marco Trevisan	Alessio Bosca
	T1.3 Energy-efficient Cloud/Edge HPC architecture & integration requirements	CNR	Salvatore Trani	Franco Maria Nardini
	T1.4 Public & private data for AI training and data sharing requirements	WR	Ali Hurriyetoglu	Bas van der Velden

	T1.5 Industrial decision support requirements for risk prevention	AGROKNOW	Iraklis Posnakidis	Babis Thanopoulos
WP2	T2.1 EFRA Data Hub population & heterogeneous data source registry	AGROKNOW	Mihalis Papakonstantinou	Konstantinos Pechlivanis
	T2.2 Novel explainable mining & analysis methods and tools	AGROKNOW	Mihalis Papakonstantinou	Konstantinos Pechlivanis
	T2.3 Semantic backbone, data annotation & interoperability	JAKALA	Alessio Bosca	Marco Trevisan
	T2.4 Intelligent Linking, Multilingual Semantic Enrichment and Data Fusion	JAKALA	Alessio Bosca	Marco Trevisan
WP3	T3.1 Process to design, train & test explainable food risk prediction models	AGROKNOW	Konstantinos Pechlivanis	Mihalis Papakonstantinou
	T3.2 Methods & tools for prediction of long-term unknown risks	WR	Bas van der Velden	Ali Hurriyetoglu
	T3.3 Federated Learning and Semantic Interoperability	WR	Bas van der Velden	Ali Hurriyetoglu
	T3.4 Enhancing AI sustainability and energy-efficiency	CNR	Franco Maria Nardini	Salvatore Trani
WP4	T4.1 Open cloud & edge architecture of EFRA Data & Analytics Infrastructure	JAKALA	Gianpiero Sportelli	Alessio Bosca
	T4.2 Re-allocating cloud & HPC resources for greener operations	CNR	Salvatore Trani	Franco Maria Nardini
	T4.3 Deployment of EFRA Data Hub and Analytics Powerhouse	JAKALA	Gianpiero Sportelli	Alessio Bosca
	T4.4 API Gateway and EFRA Data & Analytics Marketplace	AGROKNOW	Iraklis Posnakidis	Giannis Stoitsis
WP5	T5.1 Focus Groups on AI Risk Predictions Challenges & Real-world Adoption	AGROKNOW	Babis Thanopoulos	Iraklis Posnakidis
	T5.2 Experimental Methodology, Use-case Plan, and Recommendations	AGROKNOW	Babis Thanopoulos	Iraklis Posnakidis
	T5.3 Experiments on performance, speed & accuracy	SU	Tony Lindgren	Aron Henriksson
	T5.4 Empowering Decision Support with EFRA Services, Executing Trials, and Collecting Feedback	AGROKNOW	Iraklis Posnakidis	Babis Thanopoulos
WP6	T6.1 Dissemination, Exploitation & Community Engagement	RAINNO	Grigoris Matenoglou	Stavros Tsitouras

	T6.2 Building & engaging a Public-Private Network on risk prediction	RAINNO	Grigoris Matenoglou	Stavros Tsitouras
	T6.3 Involvement in industry groups & networks	AGROKNOW	Nikos Manouselis	Babis Thanopoulos
	T6.4 EFRA Sustainability plan & business models	RAINNO	Grigoris Matenoglou	Stavros Tsitouras
WP7	T7.1 Project Management and Reporting	AGROKNOW	Babis Thanopoulos	Francesca Tsaropoulou
	T7.2 Quality Assurance and Monitoring	RAINNO	Grigoris Matenoglou	Stavros Tsitouras
	T7.3 Risk Assessment & Contingency Actions	AGROKNOW	Babis Thanopoulos	Iraklis Posnakidis
	T7.4 Data Management (and Open Science)	AGROKNOW	Mihalis Papakonstantinou	Babis Thanopoulos

3.1.3.5. Agile Teams

As described in the previous versions of this deliverable (D71.1. & D7.1.2), EFRA established a set of agile teams to ensure focused, outcome-driven collaboration across partners. These teams were designed to bring together all necessary expertise, data, and operational requirements around specific expected outcomes. Their structure enabled rapid iteration, continuous alignment, and efficient cross-partner coordination.

Continuation of Agile Teams in the Second Project Year

During the 2nd year of the project, all agile teams continued to operate in their original configuration. They met monthly, following fixed meeting slots, and played a central role in coordinating technical development, data preparation, and early integration activities. Their work ensured that each expected outcome progressed smoothly and that dependencies across Work Packages were managed effectively.

A summary of the agile teams active during RP2 is presented in **Table 5** below.

Table 5: Summary of Agile Teams Active During the Second Year

Agile Team	Leader	Participants	Monitors	Use-case Scenario
Agile Team 1: Privacy-Preserving Predictive Analytics with Food Safety Data	Agroknow	Moy Park	WR, CNR	PL.2 – Salmonella Risk in Supply Chain
Agile Team 2: Active AI Learning with Food Safety Data	CNR	Agrivi, WR	SU	AG.1 – Pest Threat Prediction
Agile Team 3: NLP for Food Safety and Regulatory Data	SU	SGS, JAKALA	AK, CNR	RG.1 – Regulatory Analysis & Summarisation
Agile Team 4: EFRA Platform	JAKALA	CNR, WR	AK	Not Applicable

Evolution of Agile Teams in the 3rd Project Year

In the third year, the agile teams were restructured and evolved to align directly with EFRA's key exploitable results (KERs). This ensured that the teams were fully focused on final integration, validation, and exploitation activities.

The four agile teams in RP3 were organised as follows:

- Agile Team 1 - Data population, intelligent crawling, and publishing of food-risk datasets, led by SY, with support from Agroknow, SU, and Agrivi.
- Agile Team 2 - Development and refinement of EFRA's predictive AI models, led by CNR, with contributions from WR, Agroknow, and SU.
- Agile Team 3 - EFRA Marketplace, ensuring availability of EFRA datasets and AI models through a unified access layer.
- Agile Team 4 - Execution of AI models through EFRA's decision-support tools, enabling end-user workflows and operational validation.

These agile teams continued to meet monthly, maintaining the same fixed scheduling pattern established in RP2.

3.1.3.6. International Steering Committee

The International Steering Committee (ISC), operating through EFRA's Advisory Board, plays a central role in ensuring that the project remains scientifically robust, strategically aligned, and responsive to the evolving needs of the global food safety ecosystem. As an external, multidisciplinary body, the ISC brings together expertise from academia, regulatory authorities, industry, and research organisations. Its mandate is to provide independent guidance, validate EFRA's technical direction, and ensure that the project's outputs reflect real-world priorities and emerging trends in AI-enabled food risk intelligence.

Throughout the project, the ISC has acted as a bridge between EFRA and the broader food safety community, offering critical insights on data quality, predictive modelling, regulatory expectations, and industry adoption. During the second iteration of activities, the ISC's engagement intensified, with multiple structured interactions designed to review EFRA's progress, assess the maturity of its use-cases, and guide the refinement of its methodologies. These engagements also helped position EFRA within wider discussions on the future of AI in food safety, risk prevention, and regulatory innovation.

The ISC's contributions were captured in the updated Deliverable D5.1, which documents a series of expert consultations, working sessions, and thematic events. These activities not only validated EFRA's technical achievements but also provided actionable recommendations that informed the project's final development and exploitation strategy. The ISC's involvement ensured that EFRA's outputs remained credible, relevant, and aligned with the expectations of scientific, regulatory, and industrial stakeholders.

Summary of ISC Activities:

- Annual review of EFRA's progress, challenges, and achievements in AI-enabled food risk prediction.
- Working Group Session to present updated EFRA results and gather structured expert feedback.
- Delphi-based recommendation process to refine modelling, data integration, sampling strategies, and validation priorities.
- Live Focus Group on predicted food safety trends and global risk patterns.
- Live Tutorial on AI food risk analytics and regulatory intelligence.
- Publication of a White Discussion Paper on the potential of AI in food risk prevention.
- Continuous engagement with scientific, regulatory, and industry stakeholders through webinars, consultations, and dissemination activities.

3.1.4. Management Procedures

EFRA's management procedures ensure that the project is implemented according to the Grant Agreement, the Description of Action (DoA), and the detailed work package and task plans. Project and quality management activities support the timely execution of work, the monitoring of progress, and the early identification of risks or deviations. Decisions are normally taken by the responsible team members, following the established governance structure and respecting the contractual commitments of each partner.

3.1.4.1. Monitoring Objectives, Key Results and Major Milestones

To strengthen coordination and improve the efficiency of project monitoring, EFRA developed an online OKR (Objectives and Key Results) monitoring tool, enabling real-time visibility of progress across all Work Packages. The tool, implemented using Google Sheets, is accessible to all partners and updated directly by the WP Leaders. It provides a unified view of:

- Objectives (the strategic goals to be achieved)
- Key Results (measurable indicators of progress)
- Major milestones and dependencies
- Traffic-light status (red–yellow–green) for each reporting period

The OKRs operate on a six-month cycle, with new objectives and key results defined every semester. Before each monthly WP Leaders' call, all WP Leaders update the status of their OKRs, enabling a concise reporting round and ensuring that any emerging risks or delays are identified early.

This shared monitoring environment allows the PCO and the entire consortium to track progress transparently and consistently. It also supports alignment across WPs, facilitates cross-team coordination, and ensures that all partners remain informed about the project's status at any point in time.

3.1.4.2. Issues / Conflicts

During the project, partners may encounter technical or scientific issues requiring clarification or agreement. EFRA's conflict-resolution procedure is designed to be simple, transparent, and escalation-based, ensuring that issues are resolved efficiently while maintaining a collaborative working environment.

Most issues are resolved informally through direct communication among the involved partners. When needed, agreements are confirmed through email, written notes, or meeting minutes. Technical issues that do not affect the DoA, budget, or overall project scope are handled at the Work Package level.

If a disagreement cannot be resolved informally, the following escalation path applies:

- The WP Leader is informed of the issue and convenes a discussion among the WP partners.
 - If resolved, the Project Coordinator (PCO) is notified, and no further action is required.
- If no agreement is reached, the PCO intervenes and organises a dedicated discussion with the involved partners.
 - If resolved, the PCO informs the Project Board (PB).
- If the issue remains unresolved, the matter is escalated to the Project Board, which takes the final decision according to the voting rules described in the governance sections above.

A similar situation occurred within the PC during the reporting period, where differing interpretations of responsibilities led to a temporary misalignment. The issue was managed following the above procedure: first addressed at WP level, then escalated to the PCO, and ultimately resolved through structured discussion. The process worked effectively, demonstrating the robustness of the project's conflict-resolution mechanism and the partners' commitment to maintaining a constructive and professional collaboration.

3.2. Communication

Effective communication is essential for ensuring smooth collaboration, timely decision-making, and coherent progress across all Work Packages. EFRA's communication framework combines structured formal channels with flexible day-to-day collaboration tools, enabling partners to exchange information efficiently regardless of geographical location. The project adopted a hybrid communication model, balancing physical meetings with extensive use of digital platforms to support continuous coordination, reduce travel, and maintain high responsiveness throughout the project lifecycle.

The communication procedures described below ensure that all partners remain informed, aligned, and able to contribute effectively to the project's objectives. These procedures were refined during the second and third years of the project to accommodate increased technical integration, agile team coordination, and preparation for reviews and exploitation activities.

3.2.1. Internal Communications

Internal communication within EFRA is supported through a combination of synchronous and asynchronous channels, ensuring that partners can collaborate effectively across different time zones and organisational contexts. The Project Consortium (PC) made systematic use of both face-to-face and remote interactions, depending on the nature of the work and the needs of each Work Package.

Core Internal Communication Channels

- Video Conferencing - Zoom and Google Meet were used extensively for bilateral meetings, WP-specific discussions, agile team sessions, and consortium-wide virtual events.
- Mailing Lists³ - A project-wide Google Groups mailing list ensured consistent dissemination of announcements, agendas, and updates.
- Document Repository - A secure Google Drive workspace served as the central repository for all internal documents, including deliverable templates, meeting minutes, presentations, datasets, and administrative files. This ensured that all partners had real-time access to the latest project materials.
- Development Repository - A GitHub⁴ repository was used to host technical outputs, code, documentation, and shared development artefacts, supporting collaborative software development and version control.

3.2.1.1. Conference Calls

In addition to the monthly Agile Team meetings, a monthly WP Leaders' call is organised by the PCO. Participation is mandatory for all Work Package Leaders, who may be represented by their deputies when necessary. These calls were scheduled immediately after the project kick-off meeting and maintained consistently throughout the project to ensure continuous coordination across all technical and administrative activities.

The PCO prepares and circulates the agenda in advance, inviting partners to review it and propose additional discussion points. All partners are expected to participate actively, provide timely updates, and notify the PCO in advance if they are unable to attend. In such cases, partners are required to submit written feedback on the agenda items to ensure continuity of information flow.

The agenda of the WP Leaders' call typically includes:

- Progress updates from each Work Package
- Recent and upcoming events involving project partners

³ efra-all-noreply@googlegroups.com

⁴ <https://github.com/>

- Dissemination, communication, and networking activities
- Management topics such as reporting deadlines, review preparation, and organisation of plenary meetings
- Identification of risks, dependencies, and cross-WP coordination needs

Beyond the WP Leaders' call, regular virtual meetings are held within each Work Package to coordinate technical work, align deliverables, and address emerging issues. Partners also meet in smaller subgroups whenever needed to plan specific tasks, resolve technical questions, or coordinate joint activities across WPs. This flexible meeting structure ensures that collaboration remains efficient, responsive, and well-aligned with the project's evolving needs.

3.2.1.2. Plenary Meetings (PM)

The PC holds a plenary meeting every six months, alternating between physical and virtual formats. This rhythm ensures regular strategic alignment while balancing the need for in-person collaboration with the efficiency of remote participation. Each plenary meeting is hosted by a different partner, who is responsible for organising all logistical and operational aspects, including venue arrangements, agenda preparation, and any co-located activities such as stakeholder meet-ups or invitations to external experts from related EU-funded initiatives.

Plenary meetings serve as the main forum for consortium-wide coordination and typically focus on:

- Summarising achievements, progress, and lessons learned during the preceding period
- Defining actions and measures required to meet upcoming objectives and prepare for reviews
- Discussing the organisation and structure of upcoming work across partners and Work Packages
- Addressing challenges identified in previous reviews or technical discussions and agreeing on mitigation strategies
- Outlining dissemination, communication, and management priorities for the next reporting period

Figure 1: 5th EFRA Plenary meeting in Thessaloniki, 17-19/6/25

In addition to the formal agenda, plenary meetings provide an opportunity for partners to strengthen collaboration, align expectations, and ensure that cross-WP dependencies are well understood. As the project progressed into its second and third years, plenary meetings also increasingly focused on integration activities, validation planning, and preparation of key exploitable results, reflecting the project's transition from development to consolidation and exploitation.

3.2.1.3. Monthly Online Meetings

Monthly online meetings constitute a core coordination mechanism within EFRA, ensuring continuous alignment across Work Packages, use cases/pilots, and technical development activities. These meetings complement the plenary sessions and provide a structured cadence for monitoring progress, identifying obstacles, and synchronising work across the PC.

WP Leaders Monthly Calls

A 1.5-h WP Leaders' call is held on the 2nd Thursday of every month, chaired by the PCO. All Work Package Leaders (or their deputies) are required to attend. These meetings focus on:

- Progress updates from each WP
- Progress on key project milestones
- Deliverable planning and status
- Evaluation and validation of the EFRA pilot demonstrators
- Dissemination and communication updates

To maintain momentum between full meetings, a short 30-minute WP Leaders' check-in call is held on the 4th Thursday of each month. This call provides a rapid round-table update on: (i) Immediate blockers, and (ii) Critical next steps

[WP5] Pilots & Demonstrators Monthly Calls

Pilot coordination follows a dedicated monthly rhythm. A full pilot call is held on the second Tuesday of every month, bringing together pilot owners, technical partners, and data providers. These meetings focus on:

- Pilot progress and data availability
- Validation planning and execution
- Alignment of technical outputs with operational needs
- Identification of risks and dependencies

A short 30-minute pilot check-in call is held on the fourth Tuesday of each month, providing a quick round of updates on immediate blockers affecting pilot progress

[WP3] Prediction AI Models Calls

During the third year of the project, as EFRA's predictive AI models matured, regular monthly WP3 calls (and ad-hoc technical sessions when needed) were established to coordinate:

- Model refinement and validation
- Testing and implementation activities
- Integration of models into the pilot demonstrators

[WP2] Data Population Calls

WP2 organised monthly data population calls to coordinate contributions from all partners involved in data sourcing, cleaning, annotation, and ingestion. These meetings focused on:

- Tracking progress on dataset preparation
- Ensuring consistency and quality across data sources
- Coordinating data delivery timelines with WP3 and WP4
- These calls were essential for maintaining a steady flow of high-quality data into EFRA's pipelines.

[WP4] Technical Development Calls

WP4 held monthly technical development calls dedicated to the implementation of EFRA's core platform components, including:

- The Data Hub
- The Analytics Powerhouse

- The EFRA Marketplace
- Integration of models, datasets, and APIs
- Front-end and back-end development coordination

3.2.1.4. Google Groups

Google Groups is used within EFRA as a simple and effective email-based communication channel, allowing partners to exchange information through a single shared address. It supports consortium-wide announcements, meeting invitations, and distribution of key documents.

A dedicated Google Group was created for the project

- efra-all-noreply@googlegroups.com (EFRA All-Partners Mailing List).

Used for all official internal communications, ensuring that every partner receives timely updates and project-wide notifications.

This mailing list complements the other internal communication tools (Zoom, Teams, Google Drive, GitHub) and ensures consistent, reliable information flow across the PC.

3.2.1.5. EFRA Google Shared Folder

For the needs of document exchange between partners, a Google Shared Folder has been created. Only authorised representatives of the project partners have access to this folder. The folder structure allows the partners to access administrative information as well as organise project documents according to the different WPs and tasks. **Figure 2** presents the structure of this folder.

A dedicated Google Shared Folder has been created to support internal document exchange across the PC. Access is restricted to authorised representatives from each partner. The folder is structured to organise all project materials, administrative documents, deliverables, templates, meeting minutes, and WP-specific files, according to Work Packages and tasks. This structure ensures that partners can easily locate, upload, and manage all relevant documentation throughout the project.

Figure 2: The EFRA Google Shared folder

3.2.2. External Communications

External communication covers all activities aimed at informing the public, stakeholders, and the wider scientific, industrial, and regulatory communities about EFRA’s progress, results, and impact. These activities are coordinated by WP6, while communication with the European Commission is handled by the PCO. The external communication strategy combines digital channels, targeted outreach, and direct engagement through events to maximise visibility and stakeholder involvement.

3.2.2.1. Communication with the Public

EFRA’s public-facing communication is centred around the project website (<https://efraproject.eu>), launched at M3. The website serves as the main dissemination hub, providing access to:

- Project objectives, structure, and consortium information
- Public deliverables, reports, and publications
- News, articles, editorials, and updates
- Videos, webinars, and event announcements
- Demonstrations, pilot results, and technical highlights
- Links to EFRA’s social media channels

The website is regularly updated with contributions from all partners and is optimised for mobile access. It also hosts visualisations and summaries of project processes and results, making EFRA’s work accessible to a broad audience.

Contact and Inquiry Management

A dedicated contact form on the website enables stakeholders and individuals to reach the PC. Messages are routed to an email account managed by the WP6 leader (RAINNO). Depending on the nature of the inquiry, responses are provided within 3 - 5 working days by the appropriate consortium members.

Figure 3: Contact details of the Project Coordinator and Communication Manager

Social Media and Targeted Outreach

EFRA maintains an active presence on:

- LinkedIn
- Twitter/X
- Facebook
- YouTube
- SlideShare

These channels are used to share updates, promote events, disseminate results, and engage with stakeholders. In addition to public posts, direct LinkedIn messages were used to reach targeted stakeholders, invite participants to events, and promote EFRA’s outputs to relevant communities such as food safety authorities, industry representatives, researchers, and SMEs.

Direct Engagement Through Events

A key component of EFRA's external communication strategy involved direct interaction with stakeholders through:

- Validation workshops
- Demonstration events
- Pilot-specific stakeholder sessions
- Co-creation and feedback meetings
- Participation in external conferences, fairs, and scientific events

These events enabled two-way communication, allowing stakeholders to see EFRA's tools in action, provide feedback, and contribute to the refinement of the platform, predictive models, and pilot demonstrators. They also strengthened EFRA's visibility within the food safety, AI, and regulatory communities.

Newsletter

A project newsletter is published every four months (starting at M4). It provides:

- Updates on project progress
- Highlights from use cases and pilots
- Announcements of events, workshops, and demonstrations
- Links to recent publications and reports

Subscriptions are available via the website and at EFRA events. All newsletter activities comply with GDPR and relevant data protection regulations, ensuring secure handling of personal data.

Figure 4: Newsletter subscription form and social media follow options

3.2.2.2. Communication with European Commission

The PCO acts as the single point of contact between the PC and the European Commission. Responsibilities include:

- Preparing, completing, and submitting periodic reports and financial statements
- Submitting deliverables and ensuring compliance with deadlines
- Communicating project-related questions requiring clarification or approval from the Project Officer
- Coordinating responses to EC requests and facilitating review meetings

3.3. Reporting Types and Procedures

Reporting requirements are based on the European Commission's and Horizon Europe program requirements, as described in the EFRA Grant Agreement. In addition, to ensure the proper monitoring and implementation of the EFRA project, they also have some project-internal requirements. This section describes the various report types, details by whom and how to compile them, and the project-internal acceptance procedure.

3.3.1. Report Types

An overview of the report types expected in the EFRA is provided in **Table 6**.

Table 6: Report types expected in EFRA

Type	Scope	Description	Periods	Submission
Continuous Technical Reports	Project-internal	Used for internal reporting and monitoring of work progress among the EFRA Project Consortium (all partners)	(per 6 months) Internal Reporting periods: - M01 - M06 - M07 - M12 - M13 - M18 - M19 - M24 - M25 - M30 - M31 - M36	- M06 - M12 - M18 - M24 - M30 - M36
Continuous Financial Reports	Project-internal	Used for internal reporting and monitoring of financial progress among the Project Coordinator and beneficiaries	(per 6 months) Internal Reporting periods: - M01 - M06 - M07 - M12 - M13 - M18 - M19 - M24 - M25 - M30 - M31 - M36	- M06 - M12 - M18 - M24 - M30 - M36
1st Periodic Technical Report	EC	Used for Commission's monitoring of work progress & achievements	RP1: M1 - M18	M20
1st Periodic Financial Report	EC	Used for Commission's monitoring of financial progress & consumed resources for RP1	RP1: M1 - M18	M20

2nd (Final) Periodic Technical Report	EC	Used for Commission's monitoring of work progress & achievements for RP2	RP2: M19 - M36	M38
2nd (Final) Periodic Financial Report	EC	Used for Commission's monitoring of financial progress & consumed resources for the RP2	RP2: M19 - M36	M38
Public Reports	EC & Public	Used for public promotion of work progress & achievements	RP1: M1 - M18 & RP2: M19 - M36	M18 & M36

3.3.2. Report Compilation Details

3.3.2.1. Internal Project Reports

Continuous Technical Reports

6-month Technical Progress Reports are used to monitor internal progress across the PC. All partners prepare a Partner Technical Progress Report every six months and submit it electronically to their WP Leader and the PCO within one (1) month after the end of each internal 6-month reporting period.

Each WP Leader then prepares a WP Leader Technical Progress Report, consolidating the inputs from all partners in their Work Package. These reports:

- Provide an overview of WP progress
- Assess progress against quality criteria
- Identify risks, delays, or deviations
- Summarise next steps and mitigation actions

WP Leaders submit their consolidated reports to the PCO within fifteen (15) days after the end of each internal 6-month reporting period. The PCO compiles an aggregated version for circulation to the Executive Board (EB). Templates for both partner and WP Leader reports are provided in Annex II.

Continuous Financial Reports

6-month Financial Reports are used to monitor financial progress and resource consumption (e.g., Person Months) in relation to the actual delivery of work. All partners prepare a 6-month internal financial statement (Excel format) and submit it electronically to the PCO and the Financial Manager within one (1) month after the end of each internal 6-month reporting period.

The PCO compiles an aggregated financial overview and circulates it to the EB. Partners use the template provided in Annex I.

3.3.2.2. EC Reports

Periodic Technical Reports

Periodic Technical Reports document project progress for the European Commission (EC). They are coordinated and edited by the PCO, with contributions from all WP Leaders, Task Leaders, and partners. The PCO prepares an initial draft, requests input from contributor and submits the consolidated report to the EC within 60 days after the end of each reporting period.

EFRA Reporting Periods:

- RP1: M1 - M18
- RP2: M19 - M36

Each Periodic Technical Report includes:

- Explanation of work carried out by all beneficiaries
- Overview of progress toward objectives, milestones, and deliverables
- Justification of deviations from the original plan
- Updates on exploitation and dissemination activities
- Summary of communication activities
- A public summary for publication by the EC
- Responses to the Horizon Europe questionnaire on implementation, impact, and KPIs

Periodic Financial Reports

Periodic Financial Reports document eligible costs and personnel effort for each reporting period. All beneficiaries and Linked Third Parties prepare an Individual Financial Statement, detailing:

- Eligible costs per budget category (actual, unit, flat-rate)
- Use of resources
- Subcontracting and in-kind contributions
- Receipts (for the final reporting period)

Each organisation certifies that:

- Information provided is full, reliable, and true
- Costs declared are eligible and properly documented
- Supporting documentation can be provided upon request

The PCO aggregates all individual statements into:

- A Periodic Summary Financial Statement (including the interim payment request for RP1)
- A Final Summary Financial Statement (for RP2), including the request for payment of the balance

A Certificate on the Financial Statements (CFS) is required for each beneficiary or linked third party requesting 430.000 € or more in actual and unit costs.

3.4. Milestones and Deliverables

3.4.1. Project Milestones

Table 7 presents the formal project milestones as defined in the DoA. An internal assessment usually is being carried out during the intermediate steps of milestone completion by the relevant WP leaders. Final endorsement of milestones is the responsibility of the EB.

Table 7: EFRA Milestones overview

Milestones	Milestone title	WP	Month	Description
MS1	Kick-off event	WP7, WP2, WP6, WP1, WP4, WP3, WP5	M2	Meeting agenda, minutes and press releases
MS2	DEC Plan	WP6	M3	Visual Identity, website, social media pages, Communication Strategy (D6.1)
MS3	Initial user requirements determined	WP1	M9	Requirements Roadmap available on EFRA website

MS4	Experimental methodology & use-case plan	WP5	M12	First release of supporting documentation on experiments and use-cases (D5.2 & D5.3)
MS5	Extreme Data Discovery & Mining stack	WP2	M18	EFRA Data Registry, Mining, Semantic Backbone, Enrichment & Fusion Stack integrated over Data Hub
MS6	Focus groups	WP5	M20	Final report from two advisory-board-led focus groups on AI risk predictions challenges & real-world adoption (D5.1)
MS7	Data Hub & Data Analytics Powerhouse - first release	WP4	M21	Semantic features extracted from data sources are stored in the Data Hub. Risk Prediction models (baseline) can be run on the data (D4.1 & D4.2)
MS8	FAIR data train infrastructure concept demonstrated	WP3	M24	A functional FAIR data infrastructure available
MS9	Risk Prediction Modules	WP3	M30	AI models deployed as modules in the EFRA Analytics Powerhouse
MS10	Data Hub & Data Analytics Powerhouse - final release	WP4	M36	API exposing the Analytics Powerhouse results.

3.4.2. Deliverables Production and Submission

The table (**Table 8**) that follows lists which of the deliverables will be revised and submitted in different versions throughout the project duration. It includes the type of the deliverable which may be a report (R) or a demonstrator (DEM), the due month and the peer reviewer.

Table 8: Overview of the EFRA deliverables

#	Deliverable title	WP #	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination level	Due month	Actual Month	Peer reviewer	Status
D1.1	EFRA Requirements Roadmap	1	WR	R	PU	M09	M09	RAIN	Submitted - Revision Requested
D1.1R	EFRA Requirements Roadmap <i>(revised after mid-term review)</i>	1	WR	R	PU	M21	M21	RAIN	Re-submitted - Approved
D1.2.1	Ongoing Recommendations for EFRA Work	1	WR	R	PU	M15	M16	CNR	Submitted - Requested revision
D1.2.1R	Ongoing Recommendations for EFRA Work <i>(revised after mid-term review)</i>	1	WR	R	PU	M21	M21	CNR	Re-submitted - Approved
D1.2.2	Ongoing Recommendations for EFRA Work	1	WR	R	PU	M27	M29	CNR	Submitted
D2.1.1	EFRA Data Registry, Discovery & Mining Stack	2	SU	DEM	SEN	M12	M12	CNR	Submitted - Approved
D2.1.2	EFRA Data Registry, Discovery & Mining Stack	2	SU	DEM	SEN	M18	M18	CNR	Submitted - Approved
D2.1.3	EFRA Data Registry, Discovery & Mining Stack	2	SU	DEM	SEN	M36	M37	CNR	Submitted
D2.2.1	EFRA Semantic Backbone, Enrichment & Fusion Stack	2	JAKALA	DEM	SEN	M12	M12	SU	Submitted - Approved
D2.2.2	EFRA Semantic Backbone, Enrichment & Fusion Stack	2	JAKALA	DEM	SEN	M18	M18	SU	Submitted - Requested revision
D2.2.2R	EFRA Semantic Backbone, Enrichment & Fusion Stack <i>(revised after mid-term review)</i>	2	JAKALA	DEM	SEN	M21	M21	SU	Re-submitted - Approved
D2.2.3	EFRA Semantic Backbone, Enrichment & Fusion Stack	2	JAKALA	DEM	SEN	M33	M33	SU	Submitted

D2.3.1	Report on Data Expansion and Population	2	AGROKNOW	R	PU	M15	M15	AGROKNOW	Submitted - Approved
D2.3.2	Report on Data Expansion and Population	2	AGROKNOW	R	PU	M24	M25	AGROKNOW	Submitted
D2.3.3	Report on Data Expansion and Population	2	AGROKNOW	R	PU	M36	M37	AGROKNOW	Submitted
D3.1.1	Models and Components for Risk Prediction	3	CNR	DEM	SEN	M15	M15	WR	Submitted - Requested revision
D3.1.1R	Models and Components for Risk Prediction <i>(revised after mid-term review)</i>	3	CNR	DEM	SEN	M21	M21	WR	Re-submitted - Approved
D3.1.2	Models and Components for Risk Prediction	3	CNR	DEM	SEN	M24	M24	WR	Submitted
D3.1.3	Models and Components for Risk Prediction	3	CNR	DEM	SEN	M30	M30	WR	Submitted
D3.2	Report on Deployment of Risk Prediction Modules	3	CNR	R	PU	M30	M30	WR	Submitted
D4.1.1	EFRA Architecture & Green Operations	4	CNR	DEM	PU	M10	M10	JAKALA	Submitted - Requested revision
D4.1.1R	EFRA Architecture & Green Operations <i>(revised after mid-term review)</i>	4	CNR	DEM	PU	M21	M21	JAKALA	Re-submitted - Approved
D4.1.2	EFRA Architecture & Green Operations	4	CNR	DEM	PU	M21	M23	JAKALA	Submitted
D4.1.3	EFRA Architecture & Green Operations	4	CNR	DEM	PU	M33	M33	JAKALA	Submitted
D4.2.1	EFRA Data Hub & Analytics Powerhouse	4	JAKALA	DEM	SEN	M12	M12	AGROKNOW	Submitted - Requested revision
D4.2.1R	EFRA Data Hub & Analytics Powerhouse <i>(revised after mid-term review)</i>	4	JAKALA	DEM	SEN	M21	M21	AGROKNOW	Re-submitted - Approved
D4.2.2	EFRA Data Hub & Analytics Powerhouse	4	JAKALA	DEM	SEN	M21	M23	AGROKNOW	Submitted
D4.2.3	EFRA Data Hub & Analytics Powerhouse	4	JAKALA	DEM	SEN	M33	M33	AGROKNOW	Submitted

D4.3.1	EFRA API Gateway and Data & Analytics Marketplace	4	AGROKNOW	DEM	PU	M12	M12	CNR	Submitted - Requested revision
D4.3.1R	EFRA API Gateway and Data & Analytics Marketplace <i>(revised after mid-term review)</i>	4	AGROKNOW	DEM	PU	M21	M21	CNR	Re-submitted - Approved
D4.3.2	EFRA API Gateway and Data & Analytics Marketplace	4	AGROKNOW	DEM	PU	M24	M25	CNR	Submitted
D4.3.3	EFRA API Gateway and Data & Analytics Marketplace	4	AGROKNOW	DEM	PU	M36	M37	CNR	Submitted
D5.1.1	Focus Group Recommendations for AI Risk Predictions	5	AGROKNOW	R	PU	M08	M08	CNR	Submitted
D5.1.2	Focus Group Recommendations for AI Risk Predictions	5	AGROKNOW	R	PU	M20	M20	CNR	Submitted
D5.2.1	Experimental Methodology, Tools & Reports from Experiments	5	SU	R	PU	M12	M12	AGRIVI	Submitted
D5.2.2	Experimental Methodology, Tools & Reports from Experiments	5	SU	R	PU	M21	M23	AGRIVI	Submitted
D5.2.3	Experimental Methodology, Tools & Reports from Experiments	5	SU	R	PU	M33	M37	AGRIVI	Submitted
D5.3.1	Use-case Plan, Reports & Recommendations	5	AGROKNOW	R	PU	M12	M12	JAKALA	Submitted - Requested revision
D5.3.1R	Use-case Plan, Reports & Recommendations <i>(revised after mid-term review)</i>	5	AGROKNOW	R	PU	M21	M21	JAKALA	Re-submitted - Approved
D5.3.2	Use-case Plan, Reports & Recommendations	5	AGROKNOW	R	PU	M24	M25	JAKALA	Submitted
D5.3.3	Use-case Plan, Reports & Recommendations	5	AGROKNOW	R	PU	M33	M37	JAKALA	Submitted
D5.4.1	V1- EFRA Software Demonstrators for Decision Support	5	AGROKNOW	DEM	PU	M24	M25	CNR	Submitted

D5.4.2	V2- EFRA Software Demonstrators for Decision Support	5	AGROKNOW	DEM	PU	M36	M37	CNR	Submitted
D6.1.1	Dissemination, exploitation, communication plan	6	RAINNO	R	PU	M03	M03	AGROKNOW	Submitted
D6.1.2	Dissemination, exploitation, communication plan	6	RAINNO	R	PU	M12	M12	AGROKNOW	Submitted - Requested revision
D6.1.2R	Dissemination, exploitation, communication plan <i>(revised after mid-term review)</i>	6	RAINNO	R	PU	M21	M21	AGROKNOW	Re-submitted - Approved
D6.1.3	Dissemination, exploitation, communication plan	6	RAINNO	R	PU	M24	M24	AGROKNOW	Submitted
D6.1.4	Dissemination, exploitation, communication plan	6	RAINNO	R	PU	M36	M37	AGROKNOW	Submitted
D6.2.1	Integrated toolset for multiplying impact	6	RAINNO	R	PU	M12	M12	AGRIVI	Submitted - Requested revision
D6.2.1R	Integrated toolset for multiplying impact <i>(revised after mid-term review)</i>	6	RAINNO	R	PU	M21	M21	AGRIVI	Re-submitted - Approved
6.2.2	Integrated toolset for multiplying impact	6	RAINNO	R	PU	M24	M25	AGRIVI	Submitted
6.2.3	Integrated toolset for multiplying impact	6	RAINNO	R	PU	M36	M37	AGRIVI	Submitted
D7.1.1	Project Management Handbook	7	AGROKNOW	R	PU	M04	M07	RAINNO	Submitted
D7.1.2	Project Management Handbook	7	AGROKNOW	R	PU	M18	M18	RAINNO	Submitted
D7.1.3	Project Management Handbook	7	AGROKNOW	R	PU	M36	M37	RAINNO	Submitted
D7.2.1	Data Management Plan	7	AGROKNOW	DMP	SEN	M06	M06	AGRIVI	Submitted
D7.2.2	Data Management Plan	7	AGROKNOW	DMP	SEN	M18	M18	AGRIVI	Submitted
D7.2.3	Data Management Plan	7	AGROKNOW	DMP	SEN	M36	M37	AGRIVI	Submitted

3.4.2.1. Deliverable Submission to the European Commission

Deliverables must be submitted on the due dates specified in **Table 8**, with no contractually permitted delay. Any anticipated delay must be reported in the 6-month internal Technical Progress Report. If one or more partners are late in providing their contributions, the PCO may proceed with submitting the available deliverables to the European Commission (EC).

Deliverables are typically written reports but may also take other forms (e.g., software, datasets, presentations, or living documents). In such cases, the deliverable must still be accompanied by a written document describing the achievement and providing any relevant supporting material (manuals, guidelines, documentation, etc.).

All deliverables are submitted electronically to the EC as specified in the Description of Action (DoA). Each document deliverable must follow the standard EFRA template and preparation guidelines (see Annex I).

If no modifications are requested by the EC, deliverables are deemed approved 45 days after receipt. Approval does not exempt the PC from potential audits or reviews.

If, following evaluation, the EC considers that the PC's performance is not satisfactory, it may:

- Reject the submitted reports and request completion or revision within a specified deadline, after which revised deliverables must be re-submitted.
- Approve the reports but place the project under re-negotiation, which may include temporary suspension.
- Terminate the Grant Agreement in severe cases.

The formal approval of deliverables forms part of the External Review process (see Section 3.5).

Quality Improvements Following the Mid-term Review

Following the Mid-term Review, the EC provided specific comments regarding the quality, clarity, and consistency of several deliverables. In response, the PC strengthened its internal processes to ensure higher-quality submissions in the second reporting period. Key improvements included:

- A stronger focus on the accuracy, completeness, and clarity of content.
- Systematic checks to address typos, formatting inconsistencies, and structural issues.
- Additional internal review time allocated before submission, allowing WP Leaders and contributors to refine their inputs.
- Ensuring clear and explicit links between deliverables, particularly those that are interdependent within the same WP or across WPs.
- Avoiding inconsistencies or gaps by verifying that each deliverable's outcomes align with the overall project progress and with related deliverables.

To support this process, the Table of Contents (ToC) for each deliverable was prepared several months in advance, ensuring sufficient time for alignment, cross-checking with other deliverables, and iterative refinement across the PC.

3.4.2.2. Production of Deliverables

For the timely and coordinated production of deliverables, the PCO has prepared an advance work schedule and recommends that partners follow the process illustrated in **Figure 5**. The complete deliverables list, including due month, lead partner, type, and dissemination level, has been shared with all partners through a monitoring Google Sheet. This sheet also includes the work plan, instructions, and internal deadlines to support consistent preparation across the PC.

Deliverables are created and collaboratively edited within the project's Google Drive workspace, which ensures version control, transparency, and easy access for all contributors. Drafts undergo internal review not only by the responsible partner but, when needed, also receive a final check for style, clarity, and

language by the PCO. The WP Leader responsible for the deliverable provides the final internal approval before submission.

Deliverables planned as public are monitored through the project website, where they are made available once approved and submitted.

Figure 5: Summary of the deliverable preparation process as presented to the responsible partners and lead authors

The PCO is responsible for submitting deliverables to the EC's Funding & Tenders Portal. Submission status is tracked internally by documenting planned deadlines, delays, and actual submission dates. Overdue deliverables are monitored continuously and discussed during the PC's monthly calls. Regular reminders are sent by email, and deliverable owners are required to provide progress updates and explanations for any delays.

If a delay exceeds one month, the PCO informs the Project Officer (PO) and provides the relevant context, including feedback from the partners involved in the respective WP and deliverable.

3.4.3. Open Access

The EFRA Project Consortium (PC) fully complies with the Horizon Europe Open Access requirements and ensures that all public project outputs are openly accessible. Open access refers to providing online, free-of-charge access to scientific information for any user.

All public deliverables are uploaded to Zenodo, an EU-funded repository (OpenAIRE) that provides persistent DOIs for long-term accessibility and discoverability. Zenodo also serves as a potential repository for future datasets, publications, and other scientific outputs generated by the project.

The PC applies recognised Open Access routes, including Gold and Green Open Access, and prioritises journals and publishers that support these models. Partners may use institutional repositories or Zenodo to deposit pre-prints or accepted manuscripts, ensuring compliance with Horizon Europe guidelines on open access to scientific publications and research data.

Figure 6: Deliverables production and submission timing and submission on Zenodo

If a journal does not offer an Open Access option, beneficiaries must still ensure open access by:

- Depositing a machine-readable copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript in a scientific repository as soon as possible and no later than the publication date.
- Ensuring open access to the deposited publication via the EFRA website:
 - immediately upon publication if a free version is available, or
 - within six months in all other cases.
- Providing open access to the bibliographic metadata, including:
 - “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon Europe”
 - EFRA project name, acronym, and grant number
 - Publication date and any embargo period
 - A persistent identifier (e.g., DOI)

Table 9: Main characteristics of Green and Gold open access models

OA TYPE	Journals	STEP 1: Deposition on repository	STEP 2: Date of access	Bibliographic Metadata	Research Data (needed to validate results)
GOLD	- Open Access Journals - Hybrid Journals	Compulsory	At the latest on the date of publication	["European Union (EU)" and "Horizon Europe"]. - the name of the action, acronym and the grant number.	Needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publication.
GREEN	- Any journal	Compulsory	Embargo periods: + 6 months + 12 months	- the publication date, length of embargo period if applicable, - and a persistent identifier (e.g. DOI, Handle)	Beneficiaries may also aim to grant open access to this data , but there is no obligation to do so.

3.5. External Project Review Procedure

The European Commission (EC) conducts periodic reviews at the end of each reporting period (Month 19 and Month 37) to assess the progress and performance of the EFRA project. Reviews may be carried out by EC services alone or with the support of external experts appointed by the EC.

The review assesses:

- The degree of fulfilment of the work plan for the reporting period
- Completion and quality of deliverables
- Appropriateness and necessity of the resources used
- Effectiveness of project management
- Likelihood of achieving the project's expected results
- Planning and readiness for the next reporting period
- The use and dissemination of results

The review is primarily based on the written material submitted by the PC (periodic reports and deliverables). When required, the EC may also organise a hearing or review meeting with project representatives. The timing of the review is set to ensure that the deadlines for report submission and approval can be met, typically within 45 days after the end of the reporting period.

The outcome of the review is communicated in writing to the PCO. It may include technical recommendations for the next period or requests for adjustments to the work plan. If amendments are required, the PC prepares and submits a formal amendment to the Description of Action (DoA) of the Grant Agreement.

3.6. Financial Management

The PCO is responsible for administering the financial contribution received from the European Commission (EC) and ensuring that all financial processes comply with the Grant Agreement (GA). A dedicated project bank account is maintained for this purpose. With support from the FM, the PCO distributes payments to beneficiaries without undue delay and monitors the timely submission of all financial documentation.

Pre-financing and Payment Distribution

In December 2022, the PCO received the project's pre-financing from the EC, including the 5% retention automatically transferred to the Guarantee Fund on behalf of all beneficiaries (see Table 10). According to the project payment schedule, the first instalment, representing 60% of the total pre-financing (75%), was distributed to all beneficiaries by M3. The remaining portion of the pre-financing was distributed in M20, following the approval of the Periodic Technical Report for Reporting Period 1 (M1 - M18). Subsequent interim payments followed the schedule outlined in **Table 10**.

The PCO maintains up-to-date bank details for all partners, who must promptly communicate any changes. Partners are notified in advance of upcoming payments, including the amount and relevant references.

Table 10: Project Payments schedule

Payments schedule					
Payments by Commission	Pre-financing (75% of the total EC contribution)		Interim Payment (10%)	Final Payment (15%, including guarantee 5%)	
Distribution of payments (%)	60%	15%	10%	10%	5%
Distribution of payments (Month)	M03	M20	M25	After the end of the project	After the end of the project

Table 11: Pre-financing received by Project Coordinator

Total Funding	Pre-financing (80%)	Guarantee Fund (5%)	Received Pre-financing (75%)
4,833,797.50€	3,867,038.00€	241,689.88€	3,625,348.13€

Cost Reporting and Use of Resources

Financial reporting includes the preparation, collection, and review of each beneficiary's Individual Financial Statement (Form C) and the accompanying Use of Resources (UoR) table. The UoR provides detailed justification for each cost item and supports the EC's assessment of the financial claim. Costs must be:

- Incurred during the project duration
- Necessary for the implementation of the action
- Recorded in the beneficiary's accounts
- Supported by adequate documentation

The UoR covers major cost categories such as personnel, travel, subcontracting, equipment depreciation, and other direct costs, with explanations summarised in **Table 12**.

Table 12: Explanations for cost statements

Type of cost	Focus of Explanation
Personnel Costs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - List name, job title, cost, and person month per staff member. - PM = effective time a project member has been working in the project without illness, special leave and vacations as reflected by timesheets, for instance. - PMs should align with partner's input provided for the resource table in the periodic report. Let the PCO know if revisions are required. - Link cost items to WPs.
Other direct cost "Travel and Subsistence", "Consumables"	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - List costs per travel, name and number of attendants, place of destination, date of travel and travel purpose (special justification for travels outside Europe). - Aggregate travel costs of several attendees to the same event. - List of costs of consumables linked to relevant tasks and WPs Link cost items to WPs.
Other direct cost "equipment"	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Specify whether equipment has been acquired purely for the project (or to which extent equipment is used in project) and what it is used for. - Specify depreciation methodology according to financial regulations of your organisation. - Link cost items to WPs.

Support to Beneficiaries

Throughout each reporting period, the PCO provides guidance by:

- Supplying templates for collecting financial figures
- Informing partners about required supporting documents (e.g., Certificates on the Financial Statements, when applicable)
- Clarifying how to enter figures into the Funding & Tenders Portal
- Reviewing cost explanations for consistency, completeness, and compliance

Support is provided via email and online meetings, and all templates and instructions are available in the project's collaborative workspace. Once all financial statements are validated, the PCO coordinates the electronic signature process and ensures timely submission to the EC.

3.6.1. Keeping Financial Records

Each beneficiary must keep complete financial records and supporting documentation to demonstrate that all declared costs are eligible and that the project has been properly implemented. These records must be retained for five years after the final balance payment and must be made available upon request during EC checks, reviews, audits, or investigations.

Beneficiaries must keep:

- For actual costs: contracts, subcontracts, invoices, payroll records, and accounting entries.
- For unit costs: evidence of the number of units declared.
- For flat-rate costs: proof of the underlying eligible cost categories (no need to identify individual cost items).

All declared costs must correspond to amounts recorded in the beneficiary's accounts and be supported by original documentation. Digital or digitised records are acceptable only if permitted under national law.

If audits identify ineligible costs, errors, irregularities, fraud, or serious breaches of obligations, consequences may include cost rejection, grant reduction, suspension, termination, or financial penalties.

3.6.2. Reviews and Audits by the EC

The European Commission may conduct technical reviews or financial audits at any time during the project and for up to two years after the final payment. These may be carried out by Commission staff or by external experts appointed by the Commission. The types of audits are summarised in **Table 13**.

Partners must provide full access to all relevant records, including timesheets, accounts, invoices, contracts and payment evidence, and must supply accurate and complete information within the required timeframe, typically thirty days.

Table 13: EC Audit types

Audit	Focus of Explanation
1st Level Audit	- Certificate on the financial statements, if direct costs \geq 430.000 EUR at the project end. - Executed by external qualified auditors or competent public officers.
2nd Level Audit	- At any time during the project runtime and up to 2 years after final payment.
3rd Level Audit	- Audit in case of fraud suspicion - Executed by the European Court of Auditors and the European Anti-Fraud Office (OLAF).

4. Quality assurance and monitoring

This section describes how the EFRA quality plan defined in 2nd and 3rd version of the deliverable (D7.1.1 and D7.1.2) was implemented and monitored throughout the project, and how the mechanisms and criteria were used in practice to ensure that all outputs remained consistent with the Grant Agreement, the Description of the Action and the Project Objectives. Quality assurance and monitoring covered management processes, scientific and technical work, software development, dissemination activities and risk management, and provided the reference framework for all partners until project closure.

4.1. Methodology

The quality plan that had been defined at the beginning of the project remained the common reference and consisted of four main components:

- the main quality activities (QA, QC, QI),
- the quality management process and criteria,
- the tools/resources/templates used, and
- the roles and responsibilities of the partners.

Throughout the project, these components guided how outputs were designed, reviewed, corrected and approved, so that quality assurance was embedded in day-to-day management rather than treated as a separate activity.

4.1.1. The quality main activities

The 3 main quality activities [Quality Assurance (QA), Quality Control (QC) and Quality Improvement (QI)] were carried out as foreseen in the initial handbook. QA focused on establishing and maintaining agreed procedures (e.g. templates, internal deadlines, review steps), QC focused on checking the actual outputs against the criteria (content, structure, readability, template adherence), while QI addressed lessons learnt and incremental improvements, for example refining templates or clarifying guidance after each reporting period.

Figure 7: The key activities within the quality management process

These activities were applied in a flexible way so that unforeseen issues (e.g. new regulatory developments, additional stakeholder requirements, technical interdependencies) could be accommodated without compromising compliance with the Grant Agreement. Where recurring quality issues were detected (e.g. in early deliverables or internal reports), the PC used QI actions such as targeted support to authors, additional editorial checks or updated guidance notes.

4.1.2. The quality management process

The quality management process, as defined in previous versions of the Deliverable, was followed for all report-oriented and software-oriented deliverables and supported a gradual, time-based examination of outputs from early drafts to final versions. This process ensured that questions and uncertainties were early identified, intermediate drafts were reviewed in time, and the final deliverables submitted to the Commission met both the internal quality criteria and the contractual requirements.

4.1.2.1. Deliverable quality process

The quality criteria, as defined in D7.1.1 and D7.1.2. (quality of content, readability, structure, adherence to template) (see **Figure 8**) were applied to all deliverables, with reviewers explicitly checking alignment with the Description of the Action, completeness, consistency and clarity before a deliverable was cleared for submission. The staged process for report deliverables was implemented as designed: authors prepared an initial plan and table of contents, contributions were collected from task participants, WP leaders monitored progress and provided guidance, and successive drafts were iteratively improved based on reviewer comments.

For multi-version deliverables, later versions systematically incorporated enough context to be read as standalone documents, often via introductory recap sections or annexes summarising earlier work, which proved particularly important for technical and software-related outputs. The defined software-oriented deliverable procedure was also applied: the Technical Manager monitored software progress monthly starting from M2 before each D4.2 and D4.3 deadline, ensuring that the EFRA Data Hub, Analytics Powerhouse and Marketplace releases matched the expected functionality and quality.

Figure 8: Quality criteria (Report-oriented output)

4.1.3. Tools, resources and templates to be used

Throughout the project, partners used the common templates for deliverables, presentations, agendas, minutes and internal reports as provided in the EFRA shared folder and annexes of the Project Management Handbook. The standardised naming convention for deliverables, meeting documents and presentations (**Table 14**) was consistently applied, which facilitated version control, traceability and retrieval across the shared Google Drive and Git-based repositories.

The collaborative tools described in the handbook (i.e. Google Drive for documents, Google Groups for mailing lists, Zoom/Teams/Google Meet for meetings and GitHub/GitLab for code) formed the core infrastructure for quality monitoring, allowing the PC to maintain a transparent audit trail of drafts, comments and approvals. This environment also supported the EC's expectations regarding record-keeping and traceability under the Grant Agreement, including for checks, reviews and audits.

Table 14: Naming Standardised methods

Document Type	Naming Template	Example
Deliverables	EFRA_Deliverable No_ DeliverableTitle_Version_Date_Partner.docx	'EFRA_D1.1_Project Management Handbook_V1.0_30.06.202 2_AGROKNOW'
Agenda	EFRA_MeetingID_Meeting CITY_MeetingDATE_Agenda.docx Meeting identifiers: - KOM =Kick Off Meeting or - WPM = WP meeting - GAM = General Assembly meeting - PM =Project Meeting (concerns other meetings) or LL = Living Lab Meeting or - TM =Technical Meeting or - RM =Review Meeting or Telco =Online meeting (skype, Go-to-meeting, etc.)	EFRA_ KOM_ Athens_05.01.2023_Agend a
Minutes following the organisation of a physical meeting	EFRA_MeetingID_MeetingCITY_TITLE_MeetingDATE_ Minutes_V0.0.docx	EFRA_TM_Athens_WP2 Progress_01.01.2022_ Minutes_V0.3
Minutes following the organisation of a telco	EFRA_Telco ID_ShortTITLE_TelcoDATE_Minutes_v0.0.docx	EFRA_Telco WPM_WP3 progress_01.12.2022_Min utes_V1.0
Presentations	EFRA_MeetingID_PPTShortTITLE_MeetingDATE_Part ner.pptx	EFRA_RM_WP2 progress overview_02.12.2022_RAI NNO

4.1.3.1. Templates of reports and forms

Although this section is thoroughly mentioned in previous deliverables, we include it for clarity and continuity purposes. During the EFRA project, three main document types were systematically used to structure project work and ensure consistent quality of communication and reporting:

1. **Documents for the EC** included all contractual deliverables, periodic technical and financial reports, explanations of the use of resources and financial statements submitted via the Funding & Tenders Portal.

2. **PowerPoint presentations** were employed for internal meetings (e.g. plenary meetings, WP meetings, reviews) and external events (e.g. workshops, conferences, stakeholder engagements) to present EFRA results, progress and impact.
3. **Word documents for internal use** such as agendas, minutes, internal reports and written contributions supported day-to-day coordination and documented decisions, actions and follow-up.

Templates for deliverables were created in Microsoft Word and hosted in the project's Google Drive repository, together with templates for all other EC-facing documents. Each deliverable template contained a front cover and initial pages with essential project information and document-specific metadata, including:

- Project title, acronym, Grant Agreement number, call and type of action, together with the EU emblem and project logo, to acknowledge EU funding in line with the Grant Agreement.
- Dissemination level (e.g. PU, SEN) indicating whether the document was public or subject to access restrictions defined in the Model Grant Agreement.
- Contractual and actual dates of delivery, to distinguish planned deadlines from actual submission dates.
- Relevant WP and task number, for clear traceability of responsibilities.
- Nature of the output (e.g. report, demonstrator, prototype, website), reflecting the type of result prescribed in the Description of the Action.
- Version and status, with numerical versioning (e.g. v0.1 for drafts, v1.0 for first submission, v2.0 for resubmitted versions) and a "final" status used for the version submitted to the Commission.
- Authors and their organisations, contributors (e.g. internal reviewers), and reviewers with their affiliations, reflecting the internal peer-review process.
- A history table recording version number, date, modification reason, and the responsible person and organisation for each change, which ensured a full audit trail of the document's evolution.

Across the project lifetime, these templates and conventions were consistently applied to all EC-facing and internal documents, contributing to uniform presentation, easier navigation for evaluators and partners, and efficient record-keeping for any checks, reviews or audits under the Grant Agreement.

In EFRA, documents generally began with an Executive Summary of up to two pages, providing a concise synthesis of the document's purpose, scope, methodology and main results. This high-level overview was followed by a table of contents and, where relevant, lists of figures, tables and abbreviations/terms.

The main body of documents then comprised the following elements:

- **Introduction:** Stated the purpose and objectives of the document, expanded on the Executive Summary, and briefly described the structure of the remaining sections.
- **Main body:** Served as the core part of the document, presenting the topic in depth, explaining reasoning and justifications, and, where evaluations were included, describing the methods used, the underlying data sets and each figure in a transparent way.
- **References:** Listed the sources used in preparing the document, either collectively at the end or at the end of specific sections where appropriate.
- **Annexes:** Provided supplementary material that supported but was not essential to the main narrative.

To ensure consistent quality across all EFRA outputs, particular attention was paid to the following aspects:

- Headers and footers were formatted according to the official templates.
- Fonts, paragraph styles, bullet and numbered lists were applied using predefined styles.
- All tables and figures included captions.
- References were formatted in a uniform manner throughout.

The templates for deliverable reports, presentation slides, meeting agendas and minutes were made available in Annex I and were used systematically by the PC. When the European Commission returned a report with comments to be addressed within a specified timeframe, authors were responsible for responding clearly and succinctly to all remarks and for respecting the re-submission deadline. In such cases,

a table equivalent to **Table 15** was included in the report, preferably in the Introduction as a dedicated section, to guide reviewers to the exact sections that had been updated or added.

Table 15: Mapping review feedback to deliverable sections

Review Feedback	Sections Addressing the feedback
Reviewer's comment 1 description	Description of the added material to address the comment (where in the document) and briefly how it was addressed and where

4.1.4. The roles and responsibilities

The roles and responsibilities for quality management that had been assigned in D7.1.1 were maintained until project end: the PCO oversaw the overall QA framework, WP leaders ensured quality within their work packages, task leaders managed day-to-day quality of task outputs, and reviewers provided independent assessments of deliverables. The quality-related responsibilities described in **Table 16** (e.g. identification of reviewers, verification of completeness, validation against the DoA) were respected and regularly recalled during WP leader meetings and plenary sessions.

Table 16: Roles and responsibilities for quality management process

Role	Responsibility in Quality Management
Deliverable Author	Has the primary responsibility for the deliverable write-up, quality, and on-time submission. Early on needs to identify the task requirements, collect, and consolidate contributions, plan for the deliverable submission, and consult WP leaders and/or the TM if help is required or to report issues and delays.
Contributors	Provide quality input to deliverables on-time in sections requested by the deliverable author, and respect timelines. Help the deliverable author prepare the deliverable in relation to their contributing sections.
WP Leaders	Have the responsibility to monitor the progress of reports early on and provide support in case the author requires help. They may provide guidance on translating the task requirements and assist the report authors to structure the document correctly. They can also seek assistance from the TM or the PC if the need arises.
Agile Team Leader	Leads the agile team. They actively work on and may lead specific outcomes related to the agile team. They are responsible to set up the monthly meetings and keep the call summary minutes. They fill-in the monitoring document per agile team (see section 3.1.4.3) and updates the Project Consortium during the WPL meetings for the status and blockers encountered by the agile team.
Technical Manager	Has the responsibility to guide the technical efforts according to the project objectives and scope. At the same time, the technical manager must also guide task leaders and authors in relation to the content of the work and provide support in relation to technical questions and ensure that effective mechanisms are established to allow efficient technical coordination.
Quality Manager	Identifies possible problems and bottlenecks that might affect the on-time submission of a deliverable and the project in general. Reviews documents and performs quality checks based on the quality criteria. Ensures satisfactory readability, structure, and formatting of deliverables.

Ethics Manager	Ensures compliance of project partners to the Ethics and data privacy policies, as they will be described in the project. Outputs of the project in the form of deliverable reports or software which may adversely affect the digital privacy, research integrity and other aspects of the Ethics concerns, need to be reviewed and approved by the Ethics Manager prior to submission.
Peer reviewers	Are responsible for the technical/scientific reviewing of deliverables one month before the submission of the deliverable, to critically evaluate the readiness of the deliverable reports or outputs and assess if the task requirements are met or adjustments are needed to enable the submission of the document.
Project coordinator	Provides support, if required, to ensure the appropriate quality of outputs as well as safeguarding the well-being of the project. Performs final checks and modifications of deliverables and submission.

The Ethics and Data Management responsibilities, anchored in WP7 and in the Grant Agreement's requirements on ethics, data protection and communication quality, were integrated into the QA process, particularly for data-intensive deliverables and dissemination outputs. This ensured that scientific excellence and technical robustness were consistently complemented by compliance with ethical, legal and open-science obligations.

4.2. Quality implementation

4.2.1. Actions and decisions

Actions and decisions related to quality assurance were systematically documented in meeting minutes and tracked through the project's collaboration space, as described in previous deliverables. Action lists included task references, responsible persons, descriptions and deadlines, and were regularly revisited in WP leader and Executive Board meetings to confirm completion or define follow-up measures where delays or issues were identified.

Decisions affecting quality (e.g. on content focus of key deliverables, adjustments to templates, redistribution of contributions) were taken at the appropriate governance level, usually EB for operational matters and PB for strategic ones and recorded with voting details where relevant. Once related corrective actions were implemented and verified (for example through an updated draft deliverable or revised work plan), these decisions were considered closed, contributing to a clear and auditable quality trail.

4.2.2. Change control

The change control process was activated whenever a partner proposed modifications that could affect scope, schedule, budget or responsibilities, with change requests documented and their impacts assessed. As foreseen, minor changes within scope were handled by the PCO, while changes affecting deliverable deadlines or major outputs were escalated to the PB, and formal changes to scope or contractual elements were addressed through Grant Agreement amendments agreed with the Commission.

For each significant change, quantitative and qualitative impacts (costs, timing, resources, risks and dependencies) were analysed, and the chosen option was documented along with the rationale and any conditions. Implementation and closure of changes were then monitored through the same QA and reporting mechanisms, ensuring that the revised plans restored alignment with the DoA and with the quality and impact expectations of Horizon Europe.

4.2.2.1. Project changes requiring approval by the EC

Project changes requiring EC approval, such as those reflected in the Grant Agreement amendment signed during the project, followed the procedure set out in the Grant Agreement (Article 39) and in the handbook. The PC prepared and submitted amendment requests with clear descriptions, justifications and updated planning/budget information, and only implemented such changes after formal approval by the granting authority.

These EC-approved changes were then integrated into the quality framework (e.g. updated milestones, deliverable schedules, or adjusted objectives), and all subsequent QA activities (reviews, internal monitoring, reporting) were conducted against the amended DoA. This ensured that both internal and external assessments remained coherent with the legally binding project baseline.

4.2.3. Milestone and deliverable appraisal

Milestones were used as formal quality checkpoints: WP leaders performed internal assessments to verify that each milestone's acceptance criteria were met, and the EB endorsed the milestones before they were reported in periodic reports. This approach provided early warnings where progress deviated from plans and supported timely corrective actions, reducing the risk of cascading delays or quality issues in later deliverables.

Deliverable appraisal combined the general quality indicators (**Table 17**) and deliverable-specific indicators (**Table 18**), covering alignment with objectives, completeness, clarity, template use, audience fit and version history. Reviewers documented their comments against these indicators, authors revised accordingly, and WP leaders confirmed when indicators were satisfactorily met before deliverables were transmitted by the Coordinator to the EC via the Funding & Tenders Portal.

4.2.3.1. Milestones verification

For each milestone, the responsible WP leader confirmed that the planned outputs (e.g. requirement roadmaps, initial tool releases, focus group outcomes, platform deployments) had been produced at the required level of maturity, and that any related deliverables or internal reports were available and of adequate quality. These verifications were discussed in EB meetings and, where necessary, in PB meetings, with decisions recorded in minutes.

Milestone verification also fed directly into periodic reporting, providing evidence for the sections on progress towards objectives, deviations and corrective actions required by the Grant Agreement's reporting rules. This ensured consistency between internal QA processes and the Commission's monitoring of the action.

4.2.3.2. Deliverables appraisal and peer reviewing

All public and confidential deliverables underwent the peer-review procedure described in D7.1.1: at least one reviewer from a different partner assessed the deliverable, and in several cases more than one reviewer contributed comments for complex or cross-cutting outputs. Reviewers used the agreed indicators and, where applicable, mapped their comments to sections as in **Table 18**, making it clear which parts required revision, clarification or expansion.

Iterative exchanges between authors and reviewers continued until comments were addressed to the satisfaction of the WP leader and PCO, at which point the deliverable was considered ready for submission. This rigorous peer-review process significantly contributed to the scientific, technical and editorial quality of EFRA's outputs, including this final version of the Project Management Handbook.

Table 17: General Quality Indicators for Deliverable Submission

Quality Indicator	Reference
The proposed contents reflect the objectives stated in the DoA.	EFRA DoA
The allocation of tasks corresponds to the roles and abilities of the partners involved in the WP/ task.	EFRA DoA
The proposed timetable matches the expected submission date to the EC.	EFRA DoA

Table 18: Deliverables Quality Indicators

Quality Indicator	Reference
The deliverable reflects the objectives stated in the DoA.	EFRA DoA
The deliverable fully documents relevant work carried out in the corresponding WP/task.	EFRA DoA, project meetings
Templates are used as provided by the CO and as outlined within D7.1 Project Management Handbook.	EFRA DoA, D7.1 Project Management Handbook
The deliverable is clear and legible.	Editing in terms of correct language, formal structure and presentation of contents
The deliverable is complete.	Checking for missing parts, non-existent references, topics not covered and unclear arguments
The deliverable is covering the target reader/audience needs.	EFRA DoA
Version history is clear and well-documented.	Versioning is based on Google Drive history and stable version numbers are clearly stated on the first pages of each deliverable

4.2.4. Dissemination

The dissemination and communication activities, led by WP6, were implemented according to the objectives and KPIs set in the handbook and DoA, with continuous monitoring against the dissemination objectives listed in **Table 19**. Progress on the KPIs (**Figure 9: Dissemination KPIs**) was tracked using the updated KPI reporting tool (explained in detail in deliverable D6.1.3) (**Figure 10**), enabling the PC to adjust messages, channels or targeting where performance fell below expectations.

Table 19: Dissemination Objectives

#	Dissemination Objectives
DO.1	Engage key stakeholder segments to get feedback, validate and ensure broad applicability, replication and scalability of results
DO.2	Diffuse the generated scientific and technological knowledge within and beyond the project's consortium and put it to productive use in diverse, real-world use cases.
DO.3	Expand EFRA's outreach in target audiences via suitable key messages and customised content.

DO.4	Nurture a collaboration framework for complementarities/synergies with a) EU and global initiatives (e.g., BDVA, GFSI) towards capitalisation of project's results; b) EU funded projects concerning know-how transfer; and c) relevant networks (e.g. <i>fiin</i> , GFSI).
DO.5	Foster the acceptance of EFRA's outcomes, stimulating the appropriate market segments and sectors to support the project's exploitation strategy.
DO.6	Encourage the development of further outcomes in research, policy/standardisation and market-driven initiatives (<i>Audience</i> : Academic & Research organisations, Policy makers & regulators, Data scientists and data analysts).

All dissemination materials complied with the EU visibility and disclaimer requirements of Article 17 of the Grant Agreement, including the proper use of the EU emblem and funding statement. Internal quality checks were applied to ensure factual accuracy, consistency with EFRA's key messages, and alignment with the exploitation and sustainability plans defined in WP6.

Figure 9: Dissemination KPIs

Throughout the project, partners used their allocated effort, travel and meeting budgets to implement dissemination activities across the different tiers defined in the DEC strategy. Although these resources were included in each partner's budget, activities were planned and carried out only after consultation of the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan (DoA, D6.1), the relevant Task Leader and the WP6 Leader, ensuring alignment with the overall strategy. RAINNO developed the initial strategic Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) plan by M3 and subsequently updated it at M12, M24 and M36, providing an evolving framework for the project's outreach until its conclusion.

Planned dissemination activities were recorded by the WP6 team in the project's Google-based calendar, to which all partners had access. Partners proposed relevant events, meetings and conferences for inclusion in the events database, after which, following internal review, approved events were promoted via EFRA's online channels (website and social media).

Figure 10: The “Monitoring” sheet with the KPIs overview - Updated KPI reporting tool

After executing dissemination activities, partners systematically reported the required information (e.g. event type, date/time and location, target audience, number of attendees, volume of material distributed, contacts made, photos and contact lists) in line with the DEC plan’s instructions. WP6 maintained a central dissemination activities log, accessible to all partners, both as an online Google Docs tool and as files stored in the Google Drive repository; partner-specific spreadsheets (as illustrated in Figure 11) were created to capture all measures implemented by each organisation.

Figure 11: Partner-specific monitoring tool for monthly reporting of all dissemination and communication activities

In cases of scheduling conflicts or disagreements regarding the suitability of a proposed dissemination activity, the issue was first discussed within WP6; if no consensus was reached, it was escalated to the PCO for a final decision. Across all activities, partners consistently used the agreed templates and visual identity, thereby ensuring a uniform project image and reinforcing EFRA’s branding in all external communications.

4.2.5. Dissemination events outside the European Union

Dissemination activities outside the EU, including conferences, workshops and bilateral meetings, followed the approval procedure and documentation pattern described in **Table 20**, ensuring that potential sensitivities (commercial, regulatory, geopolitical) were identified and addressed in advance. Requests for participation in such events included justification, expected benefits, and risk considerations; they were reviewed by the dissemination leader and, when necessary, by the PCO and PB.

Table 20: Event participation approval procedure

#	Steps per period	Who	To Whom	When	Instrument
1	Send a request in the form of an e-mail explaining the reason for attending the meeting and why it is so important	Partner	PCO, WP6 Leader	>2 months prior to the activity	e-mail
2	Examine the request against the dissemination strategy and approve or reject it.	PCO, WP6 Leader	Partner	>2 months prior to the activity	e-mail
3	If the request is approved the WP6 Leader will inform the PC	WP6 Leader	PCO	2 months prior to the activity	e-mail
4	If the request is approved the PC forwards the respective request to the PO to get a provisional approval	PCO	PO	>1 month prior to the activity	e-mail
5	The PO will respond with his/her decision. The PO's decision is final.	PO	PCO	No way to gauge the time	e-mail
6	The PC will forward the PO decision to the Partner	PCO	Partner, WP6 Leader	1 month prior to the activity	e-mail

For approved events, partners ensured that the same quality and compliance standards were applied as for EU-based activities, particularly with respect to confidentiality, IPR, export of know-how and alignment with EU values and ethical standards as reflected in the Grant Agreement. Post-event reports were used to capture feedback and outcomes, feeding into QI for future international engagement.

4.2.6. Scientific and technical publications

Scientific and technical publications resulting from EFRA followed the internal publication procedure described in the handbook, including prior notification to the PC, quality and compliance checks, and recording in the project's dissemination log. Draft manuscripts were reviewed to ensure they accurately reflected project results, respected confidentiality and IP provisions, and did not jeopardise potential exploitation opportunities.

The publications contributed to EFRA's objectives of advancing the state of the art in data-driven food risk analytics, explainable AI and green computing, and were aligned with Horizon Europe's open science expectations, including open access where applicable. Relevant outputs were reported in periodic technical reports and listed on the project website and repositories.

4.2.6.1. EU emblem and disclaimer for publications

All scientific and technical publications, as well as other public communication materials, included the EU emblem and the standard funding acknowledgement and disclaimer text specified in the Grant Agreement

and reproduced in the handbook. Authors were reminded of these obligations via internal guidance and templates, and compliance was checked during the internal review of draft publications.

Figure 12: EU Emblem

Disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate): “Funding for this research has been provided by the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme EFRA (Grant Agreement Number 101093026). Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

This consistent use of the emblem and disclaimer ensured full visibility of EU funding and adherence to Article 17.2 and 17.3 of the Grant Agreement and contributed to a coherent EFRA identity across different media and venues.

4.2.7. Upload of deliverables to public repositories and EFRA website

Public deliverables were uploaded to the EFRA Zenodo community (**Figure 13**) and made accessible via the project website (**Figure 14**), in line with the open access strategy described in Section 3.4.3 and Section 4 of the handbook. For each public deliverable, the final, approved version submitted to the EC was deposited together with appropriate metadata (authors, abstract, keywords, funding information), ensuring long-term accessibility.

Figure 13: EFRA’s Zenodo community

The EFRA website provided a dedicated deliverables page, linking to Zenodo records and hosting additional communication material, thus serving as a single access point for stakeholders interested in project results.

This approach complied with the Grant Agreement’s open science provisions and reinforced the impact and re-use potential of EFRA outputs beyond the project’s formal end date.

Figure 14: Deliverables page on the EFRA website

5. Risk Assessment and Contingency Actions

Risk management in EFRA focuses on identifying, evaluating, and mitigating potential issues that could jeopardise the successful implementation of the project. Although initial risks and mitigation measures were defined in the Description of Action (DoA), risk management is a continuous process carried out throughout the project. Known risks are regularly reviewed, and new risks are identified and assessed as the project evolves, classified as unforeseen risks. Appropriate mitigation and contingency actions are defined to prevent risks, reduce their impact, or address them effectively if they materialise. All foreseen and unforeseen risks are reported as part of the internal progress report every six months.

5.1. Risk Management Process

The EFRA risk management process ensures that potential issues are identified early, assessed systematically, and addressed through appropriate mitigation and contingency actions. It is applied continuously throughout the project and updated based on progress, new findings, and unforeseen developments.

The process consists of 4 main steps:

- Risk identification - recognising and describing risks that may affect project objectives, timelines, resources, or outputs.
- Risk analysis and assessment - evaluating the likelihood and impact of each risk to determine its severity and priority.
- Risk response planning - defining mitigation measures and contingency actions to prevent risks or minimise their effects.
- Risk monitoring - tracking risks, reviewing mitigation actions, and updating the risk register regularly.

Risk management is overseen by the Project Consortium (PC) in collaboration with the Project Coordinator (PCO) and Financial Manager (FM).

- At the strategic level, the Project Board (PB) monitors risks related to the achievement of project objectives and overall WP performance.
- At the operational level, each WP Leader is responsible for identifying and managing risks within their WP activities.

All foreseen and unforeseen risks are reviewed and reported every six months as part of the internal progress reporting cycle.

5.2. Risk identification

EFRA brings together partners from multiple countries and disciplines, which naturally introduces organisational, technical, and operational risks. During proposal preparation, the PC identified a set of foreseen risks, documented in the DoA (**Table 22**). Throughout the project, these risks are continuously reviewed, and any new or emerging issues are classified as unforeseen risks and added to the risk register.

Risk identification is carried out at both the WP and PC levels. Each partner contributes by assessing risks related to their tasks, deliverables, and responsibilities. The project's management structure, regular WP meetings, monthly Project Consortium calls, and internal progress reporting, ensures early detection of issues and timely escalation when needed.

All identified risks, both foreseen and unforeseen, are reviewed and reported every six months as part of the internal progress reporting cycle.

5.3. Risk Analysis and Assessment

Risk analysis evaluates the likelihood and impact of each identified risk to determine its severity and priority. In EFRA, risks are grouped into three main categories:

- Administrative and organisational risks - e.g., limited availability of key resources, withdrawal of a critical partner, communication gaps.
- Technical and scientific risks - e.g., integration challenges, technology limitations, underperforming results.
- Business and exploitation risks - e.g., low stakeholder interest, insufficient market uptake, partner insolvency.

Each risk is assessed using a probability-severity matrix (**Figure 15**), which classifies risks as:

- Low (1 - 6, green)
- Medium (8 - 12, yellow)
- High (15 - 30, red)

This structured assessment supports prioritisation and helps determine where mitigation and contingency actions are most needed.

Across EFRA, several overarching factors may influence risk levels, including complexity, scope, capacity, reliability, validity, and sustainability. These factors are considered during each review cycle to ensure that risks are evaluated consistently and comprehensively.

Probability of Occurrence (P)	6	6	12	18	24	30
	5	5	10	15	20	25
	4	4	8	12	16	20
	3	3	6	9	12	15
	2	2	4	6	8	10
	1	1	2	3	4	5
		1	2	3	4	5
		Severity (S)				

Figure 15: Assessment of the identified risk according to its probability and severity levels

5.4. Risk Response Planning

Based on the risk identification process (Section 5.2) and the risk analysis and assessment (Section 5.3), each risk is evaluated across the three severity levels shown in **Figure 15**. For every identified risk, whether foreseen or unforeseen, the Project Consortium defines:

- the quantified risk level
- the corresponding mitigation and contingency actions
- the monitoring mechanism
- the threshold that triggers intervention
- the line of action if the threshold is exceeded

This process builds on the strategic risk assessment overseen by the Project Board (PB) and results in concrete contingency plans, summarised in **Table 21**.

Table 21: Sample Risk Methodology

	Complexity	Scope	Capacity	Reliability	Validity	Sustainability
RISK of Overall project activities	The activities are too complex to realise.	The total set of activities is too large for the partners to realise and/or manage.	One or more of the partners cannot honour its commitments.	The project methods and strategies applied are inappropriate to realise the intended outcomes.	The outcomes do not reflect the real needs and priorities of the stakeholders.	The project outcomes may not lead to a sustainable outcome.
Actions	Review the activities and/or scale down project ambitions.	Prioritise and/or scale down ambitions.	Replace defaulting partners.	Adjust project methods and strategies.	Adjust the project activities and outputs.	Adjust the project activities and outputs.
Decision Makers	PB (in agreement with PO)	PB (in agreement with PO)	PB (in agreement with PO)	WP leader (in agreement with PB)	PB (in agreement with PO)	PB (in agreement with PO)

5.5. Risk Monitoring

The Project Coordination team will manage and maintain a risk management log in the project repository. All project participants, and in particular the WPLs, will be responsible for raising any material or perceived risk as part of the normal reporting. All risks and issues will be registered in the project’s web-based risk log, and the status and mitigation of each risk element will be reviewed regularly and reported at each GA meeting. The Risk log table in the repository will comprise 7 elements:

- Number
- Description
- Likelihood to occur (Low, Medium, High)
- Risk Impact (Low, Medium, High)
- Relevant Work Package(s)
- Mitigation measures
- Status (which can be ‘Active’, ‘Mitigated’ or ‘Avoided’)

All emergent risks and issues will be registered in the risk log, and the status and mitigation of each risk element will be reviewed regularly and reported at each PB meeting. Each risk assessment is a combination of risks identified/ analysed in the previous phase and the identification/analysis of risks on current milestones/deliverables according to the DoA. In **Table 22** the identified risks by the start of the project are reported, as described in the DoA.

Table 22: Risk monitoring table

#	Risk	Probability	Impact	WP	Mitigation measures	Status
1	AI expertise leaving	Low	Medium	WP3	Re-arrange activities between EFRA partners	Active
2	Underperforming partner or Partner leaving the project	Low	Medium	All	Partners have successfully collaborated in previous/ongoing projects. Flexible management structure allows a quick shift of resources if needed	Active
3	No satisfactory interaction among WP's and tasks	Low	Low	All	Regular synchronisation among WPs will be performed to be timely recognise problems for corrective actions without significant impact	Active
4	Needed partners' resources are underestimated	Medium	Medium	All	Project management can rearrange resources among the partners as needed; commit further internal resources and replan work	Active
5	Snowball effects due to unforeseen factors, e.g., a new pandemic wave occurs	Low	Medium	All	The Project Consortium will employ all means for teleworking and remote collaboration. The work in offices and workspaces will be reduced to the minimum possible degree.	Active
6	Insufficient data available for current AI models	Medium	High	WP3	Adapt current AI models by omitting the data sources that are not available, search alternative data sources or use historical data	Active
7	Federated AI Learning approach presents significant challenges in data harmonisation	Medium	Medium	WP3	This issue will be identified early through WP1 requirement activities, so data harmonisation activities are carried out early to ensure smooth deployment of the technological stack	Active
8	No data available for the investigation of federated learning techniques	Low	Medium	WP3, WP4	Previous experience of partners in federated learning will help in dealing with the risk. An early evaluation of the risk will help mitigate it. The use of public datasets used in literature is a possible replacement for alternative solutions.	Active
9	Lack of domain knowledge in evaluating AI models for food risk prediction explanation capabilities	Low	Medium	WP3, WP4	Rapid appraisal of domain knowledge and how it maps on available data. Early collaborations with domain experts will help in mitigating it.	Active
10	Semantic Features Extraction from Data Sources is late with respect to the project plan.	Low	Low	WP2, WP4	Creation of a synthetic, mock dataset for the selected data sources. Intensive monitoring of data sources integration' progress and early identification of technical bottlenecks will also be performed.	Active

11	Food Risk data from AI models might be incomplete at M10 when the EFRA Marketplace design will start	Low	Medium	WP3, WP4	Creation of a synthetic, mock dataset of Risk Prediction. Intensive monitoring of AI model creation progress and early identification of technical bottlenecks will also be performed.	Active
12	Limited understanding by the stakeholders of the FAIR data train concept	Medium	Low	WP3, WP6	Increase the dissemination activities using industry & authorities' networks, including EFSA. Utilise pre-developed training material from partners (e.g. WR) and develop new for maximum engagement	Active
13	Low participation in the use case activities due to data sensitivity concerns	High	Medium	WP6	The AB (comprising of scientific, regulatory, business actors), will identify all relevant required technological and legal guarantees to ensure that food companies can participate without exposing sensitive data. This will be communicated to promote the focus groups high-quality results (e.g. white papers, best practices).	Active
14	Limited uptake of FAIR data train concept and developed AI models	Medium	High	WP3, WP5, WP6	Increase the dissemination activities and redesign the use-cases and focus groups	Active
15	Conflicts over ownership	Low	Medium	WP6	The continuous Task 6.5 on IPR management, will provide appropriate protection of results	Active
16	Business plan failing to exploit market opportunities	Medium	High	WP6	The business plan development leaders will evaluate, modify/customise the business plan accordingly to facilitate the exploitation of market opportunities.	Active

6. Conclusions

The successful implementation of EFRA relied on a coherent and well-structured management framework that combined quality assurance, reporting, financial oversight and continuous risk monitoring. Throughout the project, the Project Consortium applied the procedures defined in the Project Management Handbook and the Quality Plan, ensuring that all activities, deliverables and software outputs remained aligned with the Grant Agreement, the Description of the Action and the project's scientific, technical and operational objectives.

A central element of this framework was the systematic identification, assessment and mitigation of risks. Risks in EFRA could affect multiple dimensions of the project, including technical performance, data integration, stakeholder engagement, resource availability, scheduling and budget execution. By treating risk management as a continuous process rather than a one-off exercise, the Project Consortium ensured that both foreseen and unforeseen risks were captured, analysed and addressed in a timely manner.

The Project Consortium maintained a dynamic risk register, updated every 6 months as part of the internal progress reporting cycle. This process enabled early detection of emerging issues, supported by regular WP-level monitoring, monthly consortium meetings and close coordination between the PCO, WPLs and Project Partners. Mitigation and contingency actions were activated whenever thresholds were exceeded, ensuring that risks did not escalate into project-level disruptions.

Quality assurance and monitoring also played a critical role in maintaining consistency, traceability and compliance. The structured QA (Quality Assurance) - QC (Quality Control) - QI (Quality Improvement) cycle ensured that deliverables, software releases and dissemination outputs met the required standards, while the use of shared templates, collaborative tools and internal review procedures strengthened coherence across all work packages. This approach supported transparency and facilitated EC checks, reviews and audits.

Financial management processes ensured that resources were used efficiently and in accordance with the Grant Agreement. The PCO monitored cost reporting, supported partners in preparing financial statements and ensured timely distribution of pre-financing and interim payments. This contributed to stable project execution and safeguarded the financial integrity of the Project Consortium.

Overall, the combination of structured management procedures, continuous quality monitoring and proactive risk management enabled EFRA to progress effectively toward its objectives. The Project Consortium's collaborative approach, supported by clear communication channels and shared responsibilities, ensured that challenges were addressed promptly and that the project remained on track in terms of scope, schedule and expected impact.

Annex I. EFRA Templates

Deliverable Template

D7.1: Project Management Handbook

Extreme Food Risk Analytics

Dx.y.z: [Deliverable Title]

Lead Author: [Author name & Surname (partner)]

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D7.1: Project Management Handbook

Grant Agreement No.	101093026		
Project Acronym	EFRA		
Project Title	Extreme Food Risk Analytics		
Type of action	HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions		
Call Topic	HORIZON-CL4-2022-DATA-01-05		
Project Start Date	January 1 st , 2023	Project End Date	December 31 st , 2025
Project URL	efraproject.eu		
Work Package	WPx WP Title		
WP Lead Beneficiary	Partner's full name (Short name)		
Deliverable type ¹ Dissemination level ²	R PU		
Contractual due date	DD Month 20YY	Actual submission date	DD Month 20YY
Lead Author (s)	[Author name & Surname (partner)]		
Contributors	[Contributors' name & Surname (partner)]		
Internal reviewer(s)	[Reviewer's name & Surname (partner)]		

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¹R: Document, report; DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs; DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.; DATA: Data sets, microdata, etc; DMP: Data management plan; ETHICS: Deliverables related to ethics issues; SECURITY: Deliverables related to security issues; OTHER: Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

²PU – Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page); SEN – Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement; Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444; Classified C-UE/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444; Classified S-UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

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DC3: Deliverable Title

Revision history (including peer reviewing & quality control)

Version	Issue Date	% Complete	Changes	Contributor(s)
VO.1	DD/MM/YYYY	10	Initial Deliverable Structure	Contributor(s) (organization) Name
VO.3	DD/MM/YYYY	30	xxxxxxx	Contributor(s) (organization) Name

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DC3: Deliverable Title

EFRA Consortium			
#	Participant Organisation Name	Short name	Country
1	AGROKNOW IKE	AGROKNOW	EL
2	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	CSR	IT
3	STOCKHOLMS UNIVERSITET	SU	SE
4	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	WR	NL
5	MAIZE SRL	MAIZE SRL	IT
6	AGRIVI DOO ZA PROIZVODNJI TRGOVINUI USLUGE	AGRIVI DOO	HR
7	RARNNO IDIOTIKI KEFALAIOUCHIKI ETAIREIA	RARNNO	EL
8	SGS ROMANIA SA	SGS ROMANIA	RO
9	MOY PARK LTD	MOY PARK	UK

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DC3: Deliverable Title

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DC3: Deliverable Title

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Abbreviation / Term	Description

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DCX: Deliverable Title

1 Executive Summary

Goal of the executive summary section is to provide a short summary¹ for the deliverable and inform the reader on:

- The subject of the deliverable
- Summary of the work carried out
- The main conclusion(s)
- The purpose of the deliverable

¹ (text)

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DCX: Deliverable Title

2 Introduction

The goal of this section is to provide a brief outline of the **objectives** of the specific EFRA Deliverable, how those are aligned and relevant with the overall project, and what was the approach followed to **plan, do, check, act** achieve them.

2.1 Mapping EFRA Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map EFRA Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1: Adherence to EFRA GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

EFRA GA Component Title	EFRA GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
Dxy Title			
Respective extract from formal Deliverable Description			
TASKS			
Task Number & Title	Respective extract from formal Task/Subtask Description	Respective Chapters or Sections numbers within this document addressing GA described Task/Subtask	Briefly outline how addressed the respective document section(s) cover the described GA Task activities

2.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

In this section, a description of the Deliverable's Structure should be provided, outlining the respective Chapters and their content.

2.2.1 Example Heading 3

Paragraph 1 Text text text
Paragraph 2 Text text text

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DCX: Deliverable Title

3 Example Heading 1

Paragraph 1 Text text text
Paragraph 2 Text text text

3.1 Example Heading 2

Paragraph 1 Text text text
Paragraph 2 Text text text

3.1.1 Example Heading 3

Paragraph 1 Text text text
Paragraph 2 Text text text

- List example
- List example

3.1.1.1 Example Heading 4

Paragraph 1 Text text text
Paragraph 2 Text text text

Table 1: Example caption for tables

Title	Title

Text colour palette (Black text !)
 A146392 (R:205 G:99 B:146)
 A39854A (R:57 G:181 B:74)
 A1989AE (R:25 G:185 B:174)
 A414042 (R:65 G:64 B:66)

Tables colour palette
 A146392 (R:205 G:99 B:146)
 A39854A (R:57 G:181 B:74)
 A1989AE (R:25 G:185 B:174)

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DCX: Deliverable Title

Figure 1: Example caption for figures

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DEC: Deliverable Title

4 Conclusions

Purpose of this section is to summarize the outputs of the specific deliverable and how it has contributed to the overall project goals. Where applicable, do identify business impact, map business benefits with EFRA innovative offerings and record user evidence.

Here, you may also pinpoint identified best practices, elaborate on potential future improvements, and specify the evolutionary roadmap forward.

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DEC: Deliverable Title

Example of landscape layout (including custom header and footer)
Paragraph Text text text
Paragraph Text text text

Note: When using this layout, make sure that the section breaks remain in the correct place. Use CONTROL +* to switch paragraph marks and make sure there is a "section break" at the end of this page and as the last element on the previous page.

Also make sure that the footers of sections following a page in landscape format are copied from the previous section, if necessary."

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DEC: Deliverable Title

5 References

[Reference Title] [Link]

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DEC: Deliverable Title

Annex I: Example Annex title

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Presentation and Word Template

Meeting Minutes Template

Extreme Food Risk Analytics

XXX Meeting Minutes

Meeting Info	
Date & Time	
Project Website	
EU Project Advisor	
Access link or meeting location	
Virtual room (for PC)	
Tel. in case of need	

EFRA XXX Meeting Minutes / Day Month Year

Participants			
#	Organisation	Name	email

2

Meeting Agenda Template

Extreme Food Risk Analytics

XXX Meeting Agenda

Meeting Info	
Date & Time	
Project Website	
EU Project Advisor	
Access link or meeting location	
Virtual room (for PO)	
Tel. in case of need	

Funded by the European Union

Day 1: Day 1/Work Year

Time [local]	Topic	Responsible
00:00 - 00:00	Topic 1	
00:00 - 00:00	Topic 2 ✓ Subtopic 1 (Speaker's name - XX min) ✓ Subtopic 2 (Speaker's name - XX min)	
00:00 - 00:00	Topic 3 ✓ Subtopic 1 (Speaker's name - XX min)	
00:00 - 00:00	Coffee break	
00:00 - 00:00	Topic 4 ✓ Subtopic 1 (Speaker's name - XX min) ✓ Subtopic 2 (Speaker's name - XX min)	
00:00 - 00:00	Working lunch	
00:00 - 00:00	Topic 5 ✓ Subtopic 1 (Speaker's name - XX min) ✓ Subtopic 2 (Speaker's name - XX min) ✓ Subtopic 3 (Speaker's name - XX min) ✓ Subtopic 4 (Speaker's name - XX min)	
00:00 - 00:00	Wrap-up Day 1: Q&A	

Day 2: Day 2/Work Year

Time [local]	Topic	Responsible
00:00 - 00:00	Topic 1	
00:00 - 00:00	Topic 2	
00:00 - 00:00	Topic 3 ✓ Subtopic 1 (Speaker's name - XX min) ✓ Subtopic 2 (Speaker's name - XX min) ✓ Subtopic 3 (Speaker's name - XX min)	
00:00 - 00:00	Topic 4 ✓ Subtopic 1 (Speaker's name - XX min)	

Funded by the European Union

Annex II. Internal Project Reports

Continuous Technical Report Template

The template report will be accessed in EFRA Google Drive management folder. Below an example of the six-month report is presented for the progress of WP6.

Work Package No.	WP6
Lead Participant	RAINNO
Work Package Title	Requirements
Participant Involved	AGROKNOW, CNR, SU, WR, JAKALA, AGRIVI DOO, SGS ROMANIA, MOY PARK,

Deliverables for M1-M6 period	Due Date (in months)	Status
D6.1 Dissemination, exploitation, communication plan		

Milestones for M1-M6 period	Due Date (in months)	Status

Work Package Summary of Progress Towards Objectives

Task 1.1 Business Requirements [M1-M27]
Task 1.2 Technical Requirements [M1-M33]
Task 1.3 Legal Requirements [M1-M33]
Task 1.4 Data Requirements [M1-M33]
Task 1.5 Roadmap for EFRA Development & Evolution [M1-M36]
Work package partner contribution

<p>AGROKNOW</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Task 6.1: ● ..
<p>CNR</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Task 6.1: ● ..
<p>SU</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Task 6.1: ● ...
<p>Agrivi d.o.o.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Task 6.1: ●
<p>WR</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Task 6.1: ● ...
<p>JAKALA</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Task 6.1: ●
<p>AGRIVI DOO</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Task 6.1: ●
<p>SGS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Task 6.1: ● ...
<p>MOY PARK</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Task 6.1: ●

Achievements and results
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● ●

Continuous Financial Report Template

The template report will be accessed in EFRA Google Drive management folder. A template will be made available, as presented here, along with instructions.

EFRA 101093026 - 1st Internal Financial Report M01 - M06: 01.01.2023 - 30.06.2023	Project	EFRA	Start date (1st Internal Financial Report)	01.01.2023
	Organisation full name	1 - AGROKNOW	End date (1st Internal Financial Report)	30.06.2023
	Organisation PIC Number		Standard Flat Rate for Indirect Costs:	25%
	Country		Funding rate on Research:	100%
	Organisation Type			
Please fill in only the blue cells				

TABLE I: Effort (Person-Months) and Cost Details (€) per Work Package

*For the eligibility conditions for each budgetcategory please see the link below:
<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance>*

WP	PM (# of actual Person-Months)	Estimated Eligible Costs							Estimated Income			
		A Personnel direct costs	B Subcontracted costs	C. Purchase costs			D. Other costs	E. Indirect costs	F. Total eligible costs	G. Funding	H. Maximum EU contribution	I. Requested EU contribution
WP1: Requirements							0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	100%	0,00 €	0,00 €
WP2: Extreme Data Discovery & Mining							0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	100%	0,00 €	0,00 €
WP3: Data Analytics & AI Prediction Models							0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	100%	0,00 €	0,00 €
WP4: EFRA Green Data & Analytics Infrastructure							0,00 €	8.457,49 €	8.457,49 €	100%	8.457,49 €	8.457,49 €
WP5: Use-cases, Focus Groups, and Performance Experiments							0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	100%	0,00 €	0,00 €
WP6: Generating Impact							0,00 €	21.417,71 €	21.417,71 €	100%	21.417,71 €	21.417,71 €
WP7: Project Management							0,00 €	942,51 €	942,51 €	100%	942,51 €	942,51 €
TOTAL	0,00	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	0,00 €	31.566,35 €	31.566,35 €	100,00 %	31.566,35 €	31.566,35 €
Declared average Person Month rate (in the proposal stage)		5.500,32 €										
Actual average Person Month rate		#DIV/0!										

TABLE II: Other Costs Categories

WP	Cost	Explanation
WP1: Requirements	0,00 €	
WP2: Extreme Data Discovery & Mining	0,00 €	
WP3: Data Analytics & AI Prediction Models	0,00 €	
WP4: EFRA Green Data & Analytics Infrastructure	0,00 €	
WP5: Use-cases, Focus Groups, and Performance Experiments	0,00 €	
WP6: Generating Impact	0,00 €	
WP7: Project Management	0,00 €	
	0,00 €	

Please justify below the use of the different type of costs in relation to the work planned in the project